

Salt marsh distribution and structure at Langebaan Lagoon

Simone Christin van der Linden

210139595

Department of Botany, Nelson Mandela Metropolitan University, PO Box 77000, Port Elizabeth, South Africa, 6031

Email address for author: s210139595@nmmu.ac.za

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Supervisor: Prof. Janine B. Adams

Co-supervisor: Mr. Dimitri A. Veldkornet

Abstract

Langebaan Lagoon is a coastal embayment type estuary that is reliant on groundwater and contains 32% of South Africa's salt marshes. The salt marsh areas are of importance due to the number of dependent flora on residing within the system. This study aimed at identifying environmental factors that influence salt marsh structures by analysing sediment moisture, organic content, pH, electrical conductivity, redox potential, sediment content, groundwater electrical conductivity and depth to the groundwater. The results showed that each salt marsh in Langebaan was unique and different environmental factors influenced marsh species structure and distribution. Langebaan salt marshes behaved similarly to that of other estuarine salt marshes. Groundwater salinity, depth to the groundwater table and sediment moisture content significantly influenced species distribution along each of the transects, while elevation influenced the species distribution along three transects. Correlation analysis showed that sediment moisture content was correlated to sediment organic matter, sediment electrical conductivity and sediment redox potential and depth to the groundwater table. This indicated that one environmental factor has the potential to affect another.

An understanding of how environmental factors influencing species distributions within Langebaan salt marshes can aid future environmental management plans. Langebaan is susceptible to climate change and its salt marshes have decreased in the past 60 years and are currently still declining. The current management plan is not sufficient, as it lacks knowledge pertaining to salt marsh species, the salt marsh functioning and future impacts. Suggestions have been made to correct the current management plan.

Keywords: Langebaan Lagoon; salt marsh; environmental factors; coastal embayment; groundwater inflow, management plan

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1. Introduction

Langebaan Lagoon is a sheltered channel of sea situated along the west coast of South Africa. Wetlands, particularly those found in estuaries, are considered to be the most threatened habitats in South Africa (Wooldridge, 1999; Love, 2000). The lagoon is of local importance as it contains the second largest salt marsh in South Africa (Turpie *et al.*, 2002), making up about 32% of South Africa's salt marsh area (Allanson and Baird, 1990; O' Callaghan, 1990, 1994). Langebaan is a declared Ramsar site that is of international importance in terms of the number of threatened birds that reside and take refuge in the salt marshes (IBA No 105, Barnes, 1998).

Salt marshes are generally associated with estuaries. Langebaan Lagoon is not classified as an estuary as it contains no riverine input, but rather a groundwater input. Whitfield (2005) is one of very few authors who consider Langebaan Lagoon as a coastal embayment estuarine type. The lagoon system behaves similarly to that of an estuary as typical estuarine zooplankton (e.g. *Acartis longipatella* and *Pseudodiaptomus hessei*) (Wooldridge, 1999) and marine invertebrates (e.g. *Callinassa kraussi* and *Upogebia Africana*) (De Villiers *et al.*, 1999) are found within the lagoon system and the salt marshes are described as Cape estuarine salt marshes (Mucina *et al.*, 2006). The salt marshes are unique as they developed without the influence of a riverine input in a semi-arid location. Langebaan salt marshes, like all other salt marshes, are of scientific interest and conservation importance as they are unique and dynamic systems (Van Nickerk and turpie, 2012).

Salt marshes are hostile environments inhabited by halophytic vegetation. Understanding the ecology of halophytes is important as these plants enable ecologists to have a greater understanding of functions of estuarine systems. There are various processes that drive salt marsh species distributions and structures, including biotic and abiotic factors. Physico-chemical factors that are known to influence salt marsh distributions include: Inundation, sediment and water salinity, pH, organic matter and groundwater (Kim and Yu, 2009; Angiolini *et al.*, 2013; Tabot and Adams, 2013). Each physico-chemical factor in relation to species distribution needs to be assessed in order to understand the role it plays and the importance it has on salt marsh vegetation. It is necessary to indicate that environmental factors that play a role on species distribution at one salt marsh may not necessarily be the same at another (Pennings and Callaway,

1992). Langebaan Lagoon has not been extensively studied in terms of species distribution and community structures and changes thereof over time. O'Callaghan (1994) indicated that there the most extensive salt marshes at Langebaan occur at the southern region of Langebaan Lagoon and are different to the other salt marshes due to complex arrangements of channel systems. Boucher and Jarman, (1977) indicated that Langebaan salt marshes are distinguished by *Sarcocornia pillansii*. The zonation pattern of Langebaan salt marshes has been described by (Boucher and Jarman, 1977; Day, 1959; O'Callaghan, 1994).

There is a great need to develop understanding of all South African estuarine systems and associated salt marshes, as many are threatened by anthropogenic driven climate change and other anthropogenic forces. It is vital to conserve biodiversity and ecosystems and have proper management plans implemented for longevity, goods and services (e.g. food and refuge sites for local fauna species and tourism) that the semi-pristine salt marshes at Langebaan provide. Although Langebaan salt marshes are relatively pristine, there are possible threats including pollution, anthropogenic activities and climate change. This study will increase the knowledge base and provide information regarding the current status, function and health of the salt marshes at Langebaan. This could contribute to better informed management and conservation plans in the future.

The aim of this study was to:

- Map the vegetation of the lagoon.
- Determine species and habitat distribution within the Langebaan lagoon system
- Determine how environmental factors influences species distribution.
- Determine whether there have been changes in the vegetation of different habitat types in the Langebaan Lagoon from the past studies of Boucher and Jarman (1977), O' Callaghan (1994) to present.
- Assess the current salt marsh management plan of Langebaan Lagoon.

The hypotheses of this study were:

- Vegetation of the Langebaan salt marsh respond similarly to that of traditional estuarine (permanently open estuaries and temporarily open/closed estuaries) salt marshes, i.e. there are intertidal, supratidal and terrestrial zones.

- Groundwater influences species distribution; supratidal and terrestrial species are found where groundwater depths to groundwater is greater than 70 cm and the intertidal and supratidal salt marsh occur where the groundwater salinity is greater than 25 ppt.

2. Literature review

2.1 Estuaries

Pritchard (1967) defined estuaries as: “A semi-enclosed body of water which has a free connection with the open sea and within which sea water is measurably diluted with fresh water”. Day (1980) modified this definition as: “A partially enclosed coastal body of water which is either permanently or periodically open to the sea and within which there is a measurable variation of salinity due to the mixture of sea water with fresh water derived from land drainage”. According to the National Water Act 36 of 1998, an estuary is defined as: “A partially or fully enclosed water body that is open to the sea permanently or periodically and within which the seawater can be diluted, to an extent that is measurable, with freshwater drained from land”. South Africa has 260 estuaries listed according to the above definition. The most common estuarine type is temporarily open/closed estuaries.

Pritchard (1967) stated that water movements within estuaries are controlled by lateral boundaries that are important in estuarine systems. Estuaries may be subject to high rates of evaporation during dry seasons, causing hypersaline conditions, and the reverse may also occur, where a high freshwater input may cause hypersaline conditions (Potter *et al.*, 2010). Whitfield, (1992), classified five types of South African estuaries as permanently open estuaries, temporarily open/closed estuaries, river mouths, estuarine lakes and estuarine bays.

Temporarily open/closed estuaries may remain closed for short to long periods of time. Temporary open/closed estuaries are generally closed during periods of low rainfall, where hypersaline conditions may arise. Hypersaline conditions may also occur during dry periods when freshwater input is low. A combination of sand movement and reduced inflow of freshwater causes a development of a sand bar that closes the mouth of the estuary, blocking seawater movement into the estuarine (Potter *et al.*, 2010). The mouth opens when the water level within the estuary rises above the sand bar. Large amounts of sediment may be lost during periods of flooding or breaching, depending on the amount of rainfall or freshwater input (Whitfield, 1992). Temporarily open/closed estuaries experience periodic separation from the sea due to the development of a sand bar (Whitfield, 1992). Permanently open estuaries are permanently open to the sea and

wetlands or submerged macrophyte beds are a common characteristic of such an estuary (Whitfield, 1992).

(Hume et al., 2007) classified estuaries according to different controlling factors and identified eight different estuarine categories. This system of classification excluded traditional classification systems. These categories are:

- Category A estuaries (coastal lakes)
- Category B estuaries (tidal river mouths)
- Category C estuaries (tidal river lagoons)
- Category D (coastal embayments)
- Category E estuaries (barrier enclosed lagoons)
- Category F estuaries (barrier-enclosed lagoons or drowned valleys)
- Category G estuaries (fjords or sounds)
- Category H estuaries (drowned valleys, rias or fjords)

Langebaan Lagoon is not considered to be an estuary as there is no riverine input into the system. Langebaan Lagoon may behave similarly to estuaries by means of having similar species compositions as Wooldridge (1999) and De Villiers *et al.* (1999) have shown. Mucina et al. (2006) described the salt marsh within Langebaan Lagoon as a Cape estuarine salt marsh, but its function and structure may not necessarily be the same as that of an estuarine salt marsh. The classification of Langebaan Lagoon as been debated for many years.

Defining Langebaan Lagoon

Day (1959) and Schils (1998) have shown that Langebaan contains a rich diversity of both faunal and floral species and has a specific ecosystem function, enabling the lagoon to act as a refuge for many marine organisms that are not found anywhere else along the coasts of South Africa (Schils *et al.*, 2001). The lagoon also functions as a breeding ground and habitat area for many faunal species (Puttick, 1977; Maree, 2000). Birds residing within Langebaan are of a global and national importance due to their threatened status. The coastal and terrestrial regions within the lagoon provides a

habitat and food for birds, reptiles and amphibians that reside within and transcend into these areas (Saayman *et al.*, 2004).

Intertidal sandflats and supratidal salt marshes within the Langebaan Lagoon are subject to surface runoff, but are limited by low rainfall as well as by permeable sediments (Hanekom *et al.* 2009). As there is little surface water runoff, there must be a high reliance on groundwater for a freshwater supply to sustain and maintain the structure of vegetation (Saayman *et al.*, 2004). Water interaction with salt marshes is crucial. The tidal flow of an estuary brings nutrients into the system. These nutrients are derived from litter that is broken down within the marsh and become fuel sustaining the fauna associated with the salt marsh (Schils *et al.*, 2001; Pillay *et al.*, 2011).

The vegetation, south of the lagoon, consists of about 17 km of Geelbek dunes. Other vegetation types at Langebaan includes the west coast Strandveld, coastal Renosterveld, and cape Macchia (Gericke, 2008). These types of vegetation are of a high ecological value. Unfortunately some loss of the different vegetation has occurred. The reason for vegetation loss may be due to vast increases human activities causing disturbances and exploitation (e.g. Saldanha harbour). Invasive species as described by Robinson & Griffiths (2002), Robinson *et al.* (2007) and (Hanekom *et al.*, 2009), also contribute to the loss of indigenous vegetation. Saldanha Bay feeds water into Langebaan in the form of storm water runoff, fish factory affluent and sewage causing a possibility of organic matter and metal pollution (WCNP, 2013). The Langebaan Lagoon system has a limited water exchange with the ocean, causing the system to be susceptible to pollution (Flemming, 1977), especially pollution from the industrial activity within Saldanha harbour. Such disturbances as well as climate change can cause pressures within the habitat system, which is accompanied by reductions in species populations. Climate change can affect species distribution by negatively affecting interactions of species (Fuggle 1977; Holtmeier & Broll 2005; Kearney *et al.* 2009) caused by changes of abiotic factors and alterations of species as they try to adapt to new circumstances (Davids *et al.*, 1998).

Langebaan may be considered to be a Lagoon (marine lagoon), as described by Flemming (1977). This classification has been argued by Gericke (2008) as he stated that the depth and extent of Langebaan is too great for Langebaan to be considered a lagoon. Day (1959) described Langebaan to be a sheltered inlet of sea and indicated

that it was not an estuarine type. (Whitfield, 1992) agreed and excluded Langebaan from his study of estuaries. Estuarine research has been increasing and evolving allowing new perspectives of classifying estuarine systems. Lagoons can be considered a type of estuarine system, for example Hilmi et al., (2005) studied the Oualidia Lagoon in Morocco and considered it to be that of an estuary as there is an inflow of groundwater at a rate approximately $0.25 \text{ m}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$. Although Langebaan Lagoon is not a traditional estuary, groundwater discharge is known to have an influence on the vegetation (Boucher and Jarman, 1977; Christie, 1981; O' Callaghan, 1993). This can be seen by the distribution of *Juncus kraussii* Hochst. within salt marshes, as this particular species dominates areas that are low in salinity (less than 20 ppt) as a result of freshwater that flows into the system (O' Callaghan, 1993). The inflow of groundwater may not necessarily decrease salinity, as (Christie, 1981) showed that salinity of water values throughout the lagoon remained between 34 and 36 ppt. However, from a biological aspect, many estuarine species are not dependent on significant changes in salinities (Hodgson, 1987; Whitfield and Paterson, 2003). Day, (1959) observed that the estuarine round herring (*Gilchristella aestuaria*) is absent from the system but seen in traditional estuaries throughout South Africa's coasts. In essence Langebaan Lagoon may have similarities to that of traditional estuaries, but should be considered to be a unique estuarine system. Whitfield (2005) suggested that Langebaan should be classified as a coastal embayment (category D type estuary; Hume et al., 2007) and not as a lagoon, as the embayment is not restricted to the sea.

2.2 Salt marshes

South African salt marshes occur within estuarine systems that are situated along the south-eastern, southern and western coasts (Nybakken, 2001). Tidal salt marshes are important as they are considered to be areas of high productivity and sources of organic matter and nutrients supporting the vegetation and faunal species (Lefeuvre and Dame, 1994). Salt marshes are comparable in terms of primary production rates found in coral reefs and in tropical rain forests (Bromberg and Bertness, 2005). Marshes are globally recognised as wildlife conservation areas as a result of high species diversity of fauna and flora that are associated with salt marshes. The diversity reflects the complex

interactions between marine and terrestrial environments (Daiber, 1986). Salt marshes are important as they provide food and shelter for a diverse array of species.

There is no single definition for salt marshes. Authors have put forwards various definitions, some of which are based on vegetation features, others characterise salt marshes based on sediment characteristics, geomorphological attributes, etc. The only agreement between authors is the classification of salt marshes as a wetland type dominated by halophytic plants. The following table contains various definitions by various authors.

Table 1. Definitions of a salt marsh from various authors.

“...areas, vegetated by herbs, grasses or low shrubs, bordering saline water bodies”	Adam, 1990
“Saltmarshes are defined as occurring in areas regularly inundated by sea water and hence with a high salinity”	Boorman, 2003
“Saltmarshes occur in low-energy environments that aloe fir the accumulation of fine sediments.” “Saltmarsh vegetation consists of a limited number of halophytic (salt tolerant) species adapted to regular immersion by the tides.	Best et al., 2007
"...coastal wetlands that are transitional Zones between the aquatic and terrestrial worlds.” “Salt and brackish marshes are also called tidal marshes because they occur in the intertidal Zone between low and high tides.”	Weis and Butler, 2009
“Salt marshes are highly productive coastal wetlands that provide important ecosystem services such as storm protection for coastal cities, nutrient removal and carbon sequestration”	Deegan et al., 2012

Salt marsh development

There are two essential interacting inputs that are capable of producing coastal landforms where salt marshes may develop. These are energy and material. Energy is provided in the form of waves, tides, winds and biological agents, while materials are considered to be sediments, rocks and water. The interactions of these inputs are dynamic and create feedback systems which then play a role in the geomorphology of the coastal landform (Bird, 1993). In essence, salt marshes develop at land boundaries to marine environments where energy is dissipated to a level allowing fine sediments to settle enabling allowing salt marsh vegetation to colonise (Van de Kopel et al., 2005; Adnitt et al., 2007). Settling of vegetation creates a positive feedback, dissipating further energies, such as from waves and tidal influences, inhibiting erosion, by trapping sediments, and lowers salinity levels. This creates a sufficient environment with fewer stressors enabling the recruitment of floral species (Schmidt, 2013). Pethick, (2001) stated that the establishment of salt marshes responds to energy inputs in a spatial manner so as to maintain equilibrium with the “coastal energy gradient”. This equilibrium depends on processes affecting sediment deposition and erosion (Pethick, 2001; Hughes and Paramor, 2004). Any sea level rise that should occur has the potential to provoke an associated response with the adjacent salt marsh to maintain the equilibrium. A good example of this occurring was presented by (Funnell and Pearson, 1989).

Salt marsh environments

Salt marshes are considered to be coastal wetland ecosystems that are influenced by tidal inundation and are therefore defined by Lubke and van Wijk (1988) as an area located on either tidal sands or on mud flats that contain macrophytes rooted within sediments exposed to tidal inundations. It has been noted that there is an uncertainty of the zonation of salt marsh flora (Adams, 1991). Salt marshes display zonations in terms of succession and differences with abiotic components such as elevation, salinity, inundation and sediment types (Adams, 1991). Salt marshes are spatially limited to the upper most point of the equinoctial spring tides to the protected sea (Packham and Willis, 1997) and extend to the lowest neap tide mark (Cattrijsse and Hampel, 2006). Salt marshes persist only in coastal areas that are protected from waves and are considered to be contained in low energy environments where sediment accumulation

can occur. These ecosystems have high primary productivity and provide services including attenuation of floods and storms, nutrient cycling, nursery habitats for fish as well as recreational opportunities (Nicholls et al., 1999; Bromberg and Bertness, 2005).

Salt marshes are distributed across a wide range of climatic conditions and occur globally (Long and Mason, 1983). South Africa salt marshes are found along the western, southern and south eastern coasts and within a few dry river beds (Van Niekerk and Turpie, 2012). Along the east coast, the climate changes to subtropical conditions and a transition from salt marshes to mangrove forests is observed (Adams *et al.*, 1999; Nybakken, 2001; Van Niekerk and Turpie, 2012). The area of South Africa's salt marsh has been approximated to be 17 000 ha and 75% of it is confined to the Langebaan, Knysna, Swartkops, Berg and Olifants systems (O'Callaghan, 1994). The salt marsh areas are relatively small, indicating that it is a rare vegetation type and is therefore a conservation priority.

Two types of intertidal salt marshes occurring within Cape estuaries have been described by O' Callaghan (1990). The first type is associated with estuaries where tidal exchange is great, including permanently open estuaries and temporarily open/ closed estuaries. The second type is associated with closed estuaries Salt marshes within Langebaan could be considered to be of this salt marsh type. (Adams and Bate, 1995) indicated that *Spartina maritima* (Curtis) Fernald. is absent from temporary open/closed estuaries as it requires an environment where there is adequate tidal exchange. The intertidal salt marsh patterns can be related to high sediment moisture content, decreases in salinity gradients, and low redox, which are determined by the water elevation or inundation (Riddin and Adams, 2009b). If alterations within the salt marsh occur then the physic-chemical properties of the salt marsh communities change (Riddin and Adams, 2009a).

Halophytic salt marsh plant species lose competitiveness through energy expenditure of being salt tolerant (Davy, 2000). Yet competition is an important biotic interaction within salt marshes. Competition along a salinity gradient forms the upper most limits for halophytic species distribution (Kenkel *et al.*, 1991). Competition is important in determining the structure of salt marshes in less stressful environments, such as the supratidal zone. Facilitation is an important interaction within the stressful salt marsh zones (Goldberg and Novoplansky, 1997; Davy, 2000).

The primary abiotic factors influencing salt marsh distributions are salinity and water availability (Pan *et al.*, 1998). Salt marshes with a great water availability (high rainfall and intertidal zones) that is not limited will be more influenced by sediment salinity than by water availability in terms of zonation patterns (Krüger and Peinemann, 1996). Sediment moisture limits the growth of xerohalophytes (Zedler *et al.*, 1986) and may be determined by depth to the water table (Bornman *et al.*, 2008).

Salt marsh communities are generally comprised of herbs, shrubs and grasses within areas that are tidally inundated (Nybakken, 2001). Within traditional salt marshes, plant communities occur along distinct zones following a tidal gradient and elevation pattern (Hughes and Paramor, 2004; Perry and Atkinson, 2009). Salt marsh species occur in a hostile environment. Few species are able to cope in such environments and as a result, species diversity is low. Salt marshes tend to be associated with euhaline (30 to 35 ppt) conditions. Many salt marsh species are able to cope in euhaline environments, however growth rates tend to decrease (Price *et al.*, 1988) and germination occurs only when the surrounding water salinity decreases (Smart and Barko, 1980).

The species found to exist within salt marshes are determined by the specific habitats, controlled by inundation and salinity gradients (Adams and Bate, 1994). Salt marsh communities show a distinct zonation pattern along tidal inundation and salinity gradients, whereby different plant species and different vegetation colours are seen (Adams and Ngesi, 2002). Salt marshes have been divided into three predominant zones, i.e. the subtidal, intertidal and supratidal zones. These zonations are influenced by biotic interactions and by spatial and temporal gradients (Noe and Zedler, 2001; Rogel *et al.*, 2001). The subtidal and intertidal zones are characterised by stress tolerances, especially by high salt gradients, while the supratidal zone may be characterised by competition (Emery *et al.*, 2001).

The highest zone within the salt marsh is the supratidal zone that is situated at areas above the spring tide mark. The supratidal and intertidal salt marsh communities tend to be joined as one category as a result of there being ambiguity of the salt marsh macrophytes (Walker, 2004). This zone is inundated, but only occasionally. Species found in these areas are grasses, such as *Sporobolus virginicus* (L.) Kunth. and *Cynodon dactylon* (L.) Pers (O'Callaghan, 1994), the succulent *Sarcocornia pillansii*

(Moss.) A. J. Scott and *Disphyma crassifolia* (L.) L. Bolus. are also found inhabiting these zones (Veldkornet, 2011).

The area between the high spring tide zone and high neap tide, the plant species generally consist of species such as *Sarcocornia decumbens* (Tölken) A.J.Scott, *Limonium scabrum* (Thunb.) Kuntze and *Bassia diffusa* (Thunb.) Kuntze (O'Callaghan, 1994). These species represent the upper intertidal salt marsh. The lower intertidal zone is situated below the high neap tide zone to the low neap tide zone. Salt marsh species such as *Sarcocornia tegetaria* (Mill) A. J. Scott and *Triglochin bulbosa* L. are dominant in these intertidal zones (Day, 1981; O'Callaghan, 1994).

The subtidal zone is the zone occurring below the low neap tide mark. Species such as *Spartina maritima* and *Zostera capensis* Setch are found in this zone. The salt marsh ends at the spatial area of *Zostera capensis*. These plant species are known as submerged macrophytes. Submerged macrophytes are angiosperms that are found colonised in intertidal and soft subtidal mudflats and sandflats (Day, 1981). Such plant species are submerged for most hours of the day. Submerged macrophytes can be found in water bodies with salinity values ranging from less than 30 to 0 ppt (Day, 1981). Polyhaline macrophyte species (e.g. *Zostera capensis*) are predominantly found in sheltered bays and in estuaries (Lubke and van Wijk, 1988). Dense eelgrass beds can be found in intertidal zones and in shallow subtidal Zones in permanently open estuaries and lagoons. These macrophytes are only exposed when low neap tides occur. *Zostera capensis* is vulnerable to environmental changes (Weisser *et al.*, 1992).

Estuarine salt marshes tend to have distinct zonations. Plant species that are found within the salt marsh environments include *Bassia diffusa*, *Juncus kraussii* Hochst., *Sarcocornia decumbens* (Tölken) A. J. Scott, *Sarcocornia pillansii*, *Sporobolus virginicus*, *Triglochin striata* and Ruiz & Pav. *Zostera capensis* (Adams and Ngesi, 2002). Species such as *Spartina maritima* and *Triglochin striata* are found only in areas that have a profound tidal exchange (Walker, 2004). Different salt marsh categories have been identified, including the supratidal salt marsh, intertidal salt marsh, reed and sedge communities, submerged macrophytes and macroalgal communities.

2.3 Factors affecting salt marsh macrophyte distributions

South Africa is a semi-arid country and thus moisture certainly is an ecological driver for semi-arid and arid salt marsh vegetation. These dynamic interactions can easily be unbalanced by local conditions and conditions arising from the marine environment. An overview of factors influencing salt marsh macrophytes is important to for the understanding of the dynamics of the ecosystem. A single environmental factor cannot be regarded as the only responsible factor for vegetation zonation. Environmental factors that play a role to one salt marsh can also not be assumed to apply to another salt marsh, as each salt marsh is driven by a unique dynamic interaction with environmental factors (Pennings and Callaway, 1992).

Tidal inundation

The tide has been described by Boorman et al., (2001) to be a factor affecting the salt marsh vegetation distribution. Many environmental factors have shown to have to have a relationship with tidal inundation, mainly slope and elevation (Bockelmann *et al.*, 2002). Tidal inundation carries water into the intertidal salt marsh region and back into the ocean. This is important for the survival of salt marsh species. The velocity of water during periods of inundation is low, but is important for sediment accretion (Boorman *et al.*, 1998). The water edge of the salt marsh tends to reduce the velocity of the water flow aiding the sedimentation process. The salt marsh vegetation at water edges plays a role in retaining sediment by reducing re-suspension of deposited sediment (Boorman et al., 1998; Leonard and Luther, 1995). *Spartina maritima* is a common occurring species at water edges of salt marshes. The flow of water through salt marsh sediments is also important for sediment aeration and for the transport of nutrients and thus affects the salt marsh vegetation.

Sediment characteristics in salt marshes tend to show a gradient where the subtidal to supratidal salt marsh corresponds to elevation and tidal inundation (Pennings and Callaway, 1992). Salt marsh vegetation populations thus form predictable and distinct zones when grown on these elevation gradients, as shown by (Olf *et al.*, 1997). Mahal and Park (1976) showed that the productivity of salt marsh vegetation depends on tolerance to inundation. Tidal inundation is linked to zonation, but the strength of this

link is not well understood (Reaper, 1995). Salt marshes that have a small tidal influence tend to have vegetation arranged in a mosaic pattern and not in distinct zones (Silvestri *et al.*, 2003).

Salt marsh zones are based on relative heights, as similar salt marsh species occur within tide marks, not by mean sea level heights (Adam, 1981). Tidal inundation is most excessive within the supratidal zone and is thus a stressful environment for plant growth. The supratidal zone is less affected by inundation and is therefore a less stressful environment. There are however exceptions as (Pennings and Callaway, 1992) explained that some salt marshes in the Mediterranean region experience hypersaline conditions within the supratidal zones as a result of drought. Where there are high evaporation rates within a salt marsh, salinity tends to be more of a driving force than tidal inundation in terms of vegetation zonation (Pennings and Callaway, 1992).

Sediment moisture content (waterlogging)

Salt marshes are characterised by high sediment moisture content. The general trend within salt marshes is the decrease in sediment moisture from the subtidal zones to the intertidal and supratidal zones. The moisture content is greatest in regions of the salt marsh that are tidally inundated (Seliskar, 1985). The height of the water table changes twice daily as a result of the tidal influence and drainage rate depends on the salt marsh elevation, sediment characteristics and topography (O' Callaghan, 1993).

Sediments that are frequently or permanently flooded create a challenging environment for the growth of salt marsh plant species. Flooded salt marshes result in anaerobic sediment conditions. Anoxic sediments are caused by limitations of oxygen diffusion through sediments (Hemond and Chen, 1990) and by rapid consumption of oxygen of biological organisms whereby no replacement of oxygen can occur (Gambrell and Patrick, 1978). Oxygen cannot be held by sediment pores filled with water, which contributes to sediment anoxia. During a state of sediment anoxia, ions and compounds such as the carboxylic acids, CO₂, CH₄, Mn²⁺, Fe²⁺ and S⁻¹ accumulate and negatively influence the productivity and growth of plants. Plant stress increases further when subject to total submersion. This often occurs to subtidal and intertidal species. In such cases, O₂ and CO₂ supply to shoots is greatly reduced, resulting to stomatal closure affecting growth,

photosynthesis, translocation of sugars and absorption of nutrients (Colmer and Flowers, 2008; Naidoo and Mundree, 1993). Anoxic environments can be indicated by sediment electron availability (redox potential) and pH (Parent et al., 2008). Waterlogged sediments have an excess of electron donors and a lack of electron acceptors (Parent et al., 2008). As a standard, an Eh value of about +350 mV indicates anaerobic sediment conditions.

As indicated, waterlogged sediments are hostile environments. Estuaries that are temporarily open/ closed or that have a limited tidal effect on salt marshes tend to have plant communities occurring in mosaic patterns as opposed to zonal bands. This is a result of species tolerance ranges. Submerged subtidal species, such as *Zostera capensis* and *Spartina alterniflora* Loisel. have adapted greater tolerance mechanisms to waterlogging than species like *Sarcocornia pillansii* found in intertidal and supratidal zones (Maree, 2000).

Salt marsh species are regarded as terrestrial plants that have evolved tolerance mechanism to survive in saline waterlogged environments. As with salinity adaptation, different species cope with different degrees of waterlogging. Tolerance to waterlogging conditions involves an approach that waits for optimum conditions for growth. This can be seen with plant species that take on dormancy during severe waterlogged stages and includes seed dormancy (Colmer and Voesenek, 2009). This form of adaptation enables plants to survive short periods of inundation (Bailey-Serres and Voesenek, 2008).

Another strategy is that of true tolerance mechanisms involving physiological and morphological adaptations. This includes shoot and/ or leaf elongation to reduce diffusion resistance, aerenchyma development, barrier formation preventing O₂ loss, adventitious root formations, thinning of cuticles and cell walls, photosynthesis during periods of submergence, and increases in compatible osmolyte compounds and enzymes functioning as antioxidants (Bailey-Serres and Voesenek, 2008; Benschop et al., 2005; Colmer and Voesenek, 2009). Another adaptation is that of the root containing a medium exposing the plant to solutions that are non-toxic and that aid with the facilitation of effective osmosis (Adnitt et al., 2007).

Sediment composition / particle size

Another important factor that influences salt marsh species, specifically the intertidal salt marsh, is sediment composition (Price *et al.*, 1988). Salt marshes are found to exist on a variety of substrates with varying concentrations of organic substances (Burdick *et al.*, 1997). Sediment composition varies from one salt marsh to another. Salt marshes consist of sediment types such as sand, silt and clay. Bezuidenhout (2011) and Syvitski (2007) describe sand to have particles sizes between 0.05 to 2.0 mm, silt between 0.05 to 0.002 mm and clay has particles sizes less than 0.002 mm. Sediment pores, size and water aggregation rates can determine how easily water is lost or retained. Thus sediment particle sizes can determine moisture characteristics. This can be defended by Ladouche and Weng (2005) who found that compact layers of clay that is greater than 1 m deep can prevent fast recharges of groundwater during periods of rainfall.

Salt marshes that contain compact layers of clay do not receive efficient recharge rates of groundwater during periods of rainfall (Ladouche and Weng, 2005). More nitrogen is present in clay than other salt marsh sediment types (van Wijnen and Bakker, 1997). Terrestrial zones generally consist of high sand fractions in comparison to the intertidal and supratidal salt marsh zones (Bornman *et al.*, 2008). Elevated salt marshes generally contain sediments consisting of about 47% sand, 27% silt and clay and 26% organic matter and particle matter (Greenwood and MacFarlane, 2009). Salt marshes that are less elevated are generally more waterlogged than elevated marshes and sediments consist of high clay contents and organic matter (Ranwell, 1972). An interesting phenomenon is that saline sediments are able to absorb and retain water as a result of hygroscopic effects of salinity (Reaper, 1995).

Salinity (electrical conductivity)

Salinity is defined as the “total amount of dissolved solids in water in parts per thousand by weight” (Hale and Margham, 1988 cited in Reaper, 1995). Salt marsh plants are known as halophytes and are able to tolerate high saline environments. Halophytes occupy salt marsh zones where inundated water exceeds salt concentrations of 50 ppt (Long and Mason, 1983). Sodium ions and chloride anions make up a large percentage of saline water (sea water) and saline sediments (Packham and Willis, 1997). However,

sea water contains many different salts, mainly as a result of weathering of substrates (Reaper 1995). Salts are known to have low pH values, have electrical conductivities greater than 4 mS cm^{-1} and are characterised by low sodium absorption ratios (SAR). Ions other than Na, such as Ca, Mg and Mn are high in concentration in sea water and even though they are a form of nutrients, at high concentrations they are considered to be a stressor and have the potential to be toxic to salt marsh species (Rozema *et al.*, 1985).

Coastal salt marshes maintain salinity by tidal inundation. Salinity of tidal water is not considered to be constant as a result of seasonal freshwater inputs and rates of evaporation. Estuarine salt marshes tend to have a downstream salinity gradient towards the mouth, except in the case where freshwater inputs are low (Murphy *et al.*, 2003). Salinity values tend to be more varied within estuarine salt marshes due to variations in the mixing of sea and freshwater. Salinity inputs may also be maintained by wind causing sea spray. Rozema *et al.* (1985) showed that spray had a significant effect on salt marsh plant species as salt accumulated on aerial plant mass as much as $150 \text{ kg NaCl ha}^{-1}$ per annum. Salinity is not only found in the water column of salt marshes, but also in sediments. Both biological and mechanical sediment compositions tend to affect salinity (Reaper, 1995). Sediment organisms influence rates of water penetration through the sediment and through evapotranspiration by plants, salts accumulate within the sediment. The composition of sediment types play a role in determining the rate of which salts can leach into the deeper sediments (Long and Mason, 1983).

Sea water has an average salinity of about 36 ppt (Day, 1981). Tidal inundation increases salinity concentrations within sediments and factors, such as wind and sea spray add to the concentrations as already discussed. Despite negative impacts salinity has on plants, salt marsh plants are capable of persisting in saline environments. Salt marsh plants have adapted evolutionary mechanism to cope in these environments. Adaptation mechanisms include salt excretion, salt exclusion, succulence, membrane alterations and osmotic adjustments (Hameed and Ashraf, 2008; Richards *et al.*, 2009 Friess *et al.*, 2012).

According to Long and Mason (1983), the degree of tolerance of different species found within salt marshes is important as this sets the distribution limits of each species. Reaper (1995) stated that physiological effects of salinity are: osmotic, nutritional and

toxic. Salt marsh species need to maintain an osmotic potential that is low. Plants do this by accumulating NaCl ions into plant tissues and avoid enzyme interference by increasing concentrations of amino acids such as glycine (in the form of glycinebetaine) and proline and other molecules such as polyols and sorbitol (Rozema *et al.*, 1985).

Sediment organic content and nutrients

Nutrients within traditional estuaries result from riverine inputs from catchment zones and from the ocean by means of tidal exchange, but occur more rarely (Kennish, 1986). Nutrients may be collected within estuaries by means of floods contributing to productivity (Desilets and Houle, 2005). Estuaries that have reduced freshwater inflow generally result in a loss of nutrients (Day, 1981).

Sediment organic matter within salt marshes is controlled by dynamic interactions. (Adams *et al.*, 1999) indicated that intertidal salt marshes and submerged macrophytes have more important roles in terms of nutrient exchange than supratidal salt marshes. Supratidal salt marshes may however act as sinks for organic carbon (Adams *et al.*, 1999). Sediment organic content is a term to define carbon nutrients in sediments, usually consisting of carbohydrates, fats, nucleic acids and proteins. The organic component of sediment that is considered to be stable has a capacity to hold and absorb nutrients as well as a capacity to hold moisture. Humus is another term for the stable organic content. Saline water plays a role in decomposition of organic matter (Weston *et al.*, 2010). Decomposition of organic matter provides nutrients for salt marsh plant species (Odum, 1988). Nutrients are released during decomposition in a bioavailable form to salt marsh plants, enhancing plant productivity (Simões *et al.*, 2011). It can be concluded that biochemical process within salt marsh sediment plays important roles in nutrient cycling (Wang *et al.*, 2010). Primary producers are the main source of organic matter. This includes primary producers within sediment and in pelagic environments. Organic matter within sediments includes microalgae, macroalgae and macrophytes. Plankton, bacteria, plant and animal detritus all influence organic matter within sediments (Taljaard *et al.*, 2009).

Dense stands of *Juncus kraussii* are often found in supratidal salt marsh zones as a result of high organic matter within sediments (Clarke and Jacoby, 1994). Supratidal

zones containing high organic matter provide intertidal zones with its source, as intertidal zones are frequently depleted as a result of sediment microbial activity (Clarke and Jacoby, 1994). During periods of high neap tides detrital matter within intertidal zones are frequently deposited to supratidal zones (Healy *et al.*, 2002). Different macrophyte species respond differently to various sediment nutrient contents and this plays a role in competition and community structures (Pennings *et al.*, 2002).

Redox potential

Waterlogged sediments trigger a chain of reactions which cause reduced sediment redox potentials. Such reactions involve processes that are of a physical, chemical and biochemical nature and have been known to influence salt marsh plant species (Gambrell and Patrick, 1978; Gambrell *et al.*, 1991). The physical process includes the restriction of oxygen into waterlogged sediment and the anaerobic processes leading to anaerobic conditions (Pett-Ridge and Firestone, 2005). This process leads to a reduction of sediment oxidation reduction potentials. Chemical changes also take place during this process, such as the reductions of: NO_3^- to N_2 , Mn^{4+} to Mn^{2+} , Fe^{3+} to Fe^{2+} , SO_4^- to H_2S and S^{2+} to HS^- . These reductions are dependent on pH. Another chemical alteration is the accumulation of acetic and butyric acids that are products of microbial activities (Gambrell and Patrick, 1978; Gambrell *et al.*, 1991). Quantifying sediment redox potential is an advantageous as a tool used to quantify the oxygen content in salt marsh sediment.

Roots play a vital role in absorbing and transporting nutrients and solutes to plant tissues. The reason for this is that roots make contact with sediment nutrients and plays the primary role in adsorption and transportation of nutrients to the plant (Sánchez-Moreiras and Weiss, 2002). Under normal sediment conditions, the ionic concentrations between the root cells and sediment medium is high and redox potential may be between -60 and 250 mV (Fitter and Hay, 2002). The redox potential of sediments is an important environmental factor that plays a role in mineral uptake required for plant growth and functions.

When sediments are saturated, normal respiration may continue provided that there is sufficient oxygen for uptake and that plant roots are not exposed to toxic substances

(Hillel, 1971). Within salt marshes, sediment moisture and redox potential may be related. The reason for that is because waterlogged sediments have high redox potentials as a result of very little organic matter in those sediments (Rogel *et al.*, 2001). A decrease of microbial activity or decomposition of organic matter may be a reason for the lack thereof (Rhao and Pathak, 1996). Intertidal salt marshes are well known to be exhausted of oxygen and plant species survive in prevailing anaerobic conditions where organic and inorganic nutrients are limited (Packham and Willis, 1997). Redox potential is important, especially when considering the biochemical cycling of nutrients and the mobility of metals (Nyle and Ray, 1997).

pH

pH is known to define biological and chemical activity thresholds and it relates to sediment organic matter activity and stability (Gerritse and van Driel, 1984). Sediment pH is influenced by climate, biota, organic matter, and topography. The availability of nutrients depends highly on the pH (Arshad and Coen, 2009).

The transportation of anions into cells is an active process and the adsorption of anions, such as SO_4^{2-} and H_2PO_4 relates to secondary co-transporters and is associated with hydrogen protons (Sánchez-Moreiras and Weiss, 2002). The absorption rate of anions and cations are varied and cause alterations in pH, as excess anion adsorption results in a decrease in pH, while an excess absorption of cations increases pH sediment medium (Dunn and Arditti, 1969). At a low pH, metals, such as zinc, iron and magnesium become mobile and have to the potential to be toxic when accumulated by plants. A low pH can also reduce nutrient availability, such calcium and phosphorus (Ca çador *et al.*, 1996). On the other hand, at a high sediment pH, calcium and phosphorus can become abundant, while metal micro-nutrients are immobilized. (Smith and Doran, 1996) indicated that vegetation types and its productivity are highly correlated with pH and the adaptation that certain plants may have to deal with pH variability.

Elevation

Elevation as a factor influencing salt marsh species distribution has been discussed interactively with the factors mentioned above. A brief overview of elevation is presented.

Elevation is recorded as Mean Sea Level (MSL) and is defined as “the height relative to some datum, of the surface of the sea as measured at a given place and time” (Van de Plassche, 1986 in: Schmidt, 2013). Zonation of vegetation is largely determined by differentiated altitude as a result of tidal patterns creating a distribution limit for plant species to inhabit (Sanchez *et al.*, 1996). Adam (1990) indicated that sediment salinity may increase as elevation increases to above the mean salinity sea level and as the elevation continues to increase, a decrease in salinity occurs. Halophytes and elevation gradients tend to show relationships as indicated by (Bezuidenhout, 2011). Evaporation rates are higher and more persistent at higher elevations, increasing the concentration of salts (Adam, 1990). At high salt marsh elevations, sediment salinity decreases as a result of low salt input and less tidal inundation. (Sanchez *et al.*, 1996) showed that there was a significant difference between elevations and plant communities and species composition, meaning that species composition within salt marshes may be predicted by the elevation pattern. Species diversity tends to increase with elevation (Silvestri *et al.*, 2005).

Groundwater

Groundwater is another mechanism that is known to have an effect on the dynamics of salt marshes (Ridolfi *et al.*, 2006). (Bornman *et al.*, 2004) explained that the geomorphology of salt marshes and floodplains can be complex and have an influence on the distribution of salt marsh vegetation. The depth to the groundwater table and salinity of groundwater are two important determinants for supratidal salt marshes (Desilets and Houle, 2005; Ridolfi *et al.*, 2006). Groundwater influences salt marsh vegetation through sediment capillary rise of chlorides from the groundwater table to the ground surface (Cisneros *et al.*, 1999). Channels within salt marsh systems provide a water source and its surface flow depends on its distance from salt marsh species (Ursino *et al.*, 2004).

Groundwater flux may be influenced by groundwater salinity and depth to the ground table and differs during different seasons (Addy *et al.*, 2005). During winter, Greenwich Bay, Bay Island the groundwater was less saline than during summer as a result of climate variations and evapotranspiration rates (Addy *et al.*, 2005).

In South Africa, groundwater influences salt marsh species particularly those situated in arid / semi-arid areas. The Olifants Estuary salt marsh is comprised of a single dominant species, *Sarcocornia pillansii* and its survival depends on groundwater (Bornman, 2002). *S. pillansii* cannot survive in waterlogged conditions or in area of the salt marsh where the depth to the water table is deeper than 1.5 m or where the electrical conductivity of the groundwater exceeds 80 mS cm⁻¹ (Bornman, 2002) .

In semi-arid regions, such as at Langebaan, rainfall will not be sufficient enough to flush salts that accumulate throughout the salt marsh (Hillel, 1971). When groundwater is drawn up through the capillary action, salts accumulate at the surface, especially when evaporation rates are high (Cisneros *et al.*, 1999)

Climate Change

As a result of climate change, the sea level has been rising at a rate approximately 2 mm per year (Church *et al.*, 2008). Within natural estuarine systems, such as Langebaan, rising sea levels does not pose as much of a threat to salt marshes than in. Salt marshes can move landwards and its complex interactions may again find a new equilibrium. Barriers at terrestrial edges of salt marshes limit salt marsh movements. In such cases, loss of salt marshes may occur.

Sea level rise is not the only effect of global warming. Increases in average temperature, storm intensities and flow modification are predicted that will possibly lead to physical changes of estuaries and biological responses of plant species as shifts in ecosystem services may be altered (Van Niekerk and Turpie, 2012). West coast estuaries are likely to be most affected by climate change. Schmidt (2013) explained that although rainfall episodes are likely to increase, estuaries may become dependent of the rainfall to reduce harsh effects of salinity and to provide sediment through runoff.

2.4 Environmental management and conservation

Langebaan Lagoon should be recognised as an estuary, i.e. a coastal embayment. No estuarine system is considered to be an isolated system (Pennings and Callaway, 1992). Saltmarshes are specialised habitats that support halophytic vegetation able to cope with high salinity and periods of inundation. These systems form boundaries between coastal marine and terrestrial systems. Langebaan Lagoon forms part of a regional, national and global ecosystem as a result of its freshwater input being groundwater and the vast amount of fauna and flora species being sustained by it. Langebaan Lagoon is a Ramsar wetland site that was proclaimed in 1998 and is considered an important bird area (IBA No 105, Barnes, 1998). More than 250 bird species have been recorded within the lagoon area. The salt marsh supports more than 35 000 birds on a regular basis (Gericke, 2008). The sustainability of Interactions between various components within estuarine require a management play, including salt marshes.

Salt marshes have been stable for thousands of year and after disturbances, early developing salt marshes have the ability to rapidly recover as Boorman (2003) explained. Salt marshes are subject to erosion from violent storms and increases in sea level rise, which may cause salt marshes to move landwards. There have been many changes made to salt marshes on a global scale. One of these changes is that salt marshes have become less extensive due to developments and various other anthropogenic activities. Anthropogenic disturbance of an estuarine system will influence large habitat ranges, including salt marshes. Many salt marshes have disappeared as a result of developments. The conservation value of salt marshes is high as these halophytes are adapted to grow only in salt marsh systems and a loss of the salt marsh vegetation leads to dry bare salt pans that are gradually eroded by environmental conditions.

Management plans have become an important manner in which ensures the survival and protection of remaining salt marshes. Management plans are required to be coupled with monitoring programmes to ensure that the management of salt marshes is done in an appropriate and effective manner. Such plans need to be flexible and responsive to changes and should aim to ensure that management methods are sound and applied correctly. The only manner in which to do this, according to (Boorman, 2003) is to constantly review information from monitoring.

The West Cape National Park (WCNP, 2013) has a park management plan that includes the Langebaan Lagoon for the period of 2013-2023. The West Coast National Park Management prevents external damages to Langebaan salt marshes, such as excessive trampling and pollution and it aims to determine changes to the marshes over time. The main problem with this management plan is that the salt marsh is described by Boucher and Jarman (1977). The salt marsh may have changed since 1977 and those changes need to be accounted for in the management plan. It is suggested that the management plan for Langebaan salt marshes needs to be reviewed.

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Langebaan Lagoon study site

Location

Langebaan Lagoon (located between 33°11'27"S, 18°07'37"E and 33°03'54"S, 17°58'07"E) is situated about 120 km north of Cape Town in the Western Cape Province (see Fig 1). Langebaan Lagoon is found within the West Coast National Park and has a cover area of about 57 km² (Saayman *et al.*, 2004) and contains about 32% of South Africa's salt marsh area (O'Callaghan, 1994).

The Langebaan Lagoon and Saldanha Bay are separated by Sheep Island that is situated at the mouth of Langebaan Lagoon. The lagoon is approximately 22 km in length and can reach up to 4 km in width (Fig 1). The lagoon is shallow, reaching up to a maximum depth of about 6 m. The calm conditions of the lagoon have been ideal for the salt marsh formations. The most prevalent salt marsh is found at southernmost part of the lagoon (see Fig 3). The West Coast National Park was proclaimed in 1985 as the Langebaan National Park and the name later changed in 1987 and the lagoon area was classified as an internationally important wetland in terms of the Ramsar convention in 1998 as a result of the amount of birdlife the wetland supports (Reaper, 1995). The lagoon salt marsh has been protected since 1988. The Western Cape National Park places a high conservation status on the threatened Strandveld Lowland fynbos. The park contains three main vegetation types: Strandveld, Coastal Renostreveld and Cape Mucchia (Reaper, 1995). Salt marshes are found along the edge of the lagoon.

Freshwater marshes contain a high water table (Boucher and Jarman, 1977). Groundwater sustains the lagoons freshwater marshes (Boucher and Jarman, 1977; O'callaghan, 1994). Salt marshes are influenced by groundwater in a similar manner. The lagoon is not classified as an estuary, but behaves similarly to an estuarine system.

Figure 1. Study site map of Langebaan Lagoon

Lagoon geology, hydrology and vegetation

Langebaan Lagoon formed as a result of sea-level changes that formed sand dunes along the oceans coast. This occurred during the Cenozoic era. The dunes were submerged during the Tertiary era and were washed away. Today the Donkergat Peninsula is what is left of that dune system. The reason it remained is because Cape Granite is found within the Donkergat Peninsula and is resistant to being washed away. The Langebaan Lagoon contains Cape Granite, covered with marine sediment. Calcrete sheets are situated beneath the salt marsh areas within the lagoon (Reaper, 1995). Figure 1 visually shows the various geological components of Langebaan Lagoon.

The lagoon waters interchange with the Saldanha Bay waters during tidal fluctuations. During these fluctuations, approximately half of the lagoon water passes into Saldanha Bay. The residual water remains in the lagoon and partial water exchange occurs with Saldanha Bay with some direct exchange with coastal water from the Atlantic Ocean (Shannon and Stander, 1977). The water exchange with the ocean is slow and this could cause any pollution from Saldanha Bay to entering into Langebaan Lagoon without being dispersed. Day (1959) indicated that the water temperature of the lagoon increased from the mouth of the lagoon to the head as a result of the lagoons shallow nature. The water temperature directly affects the water ability to solvent gasses and therefore can affect the salt marsh performance.

The terrestrial vegetation is controlled by the different sediment types that are found within the lagoon area. The different sediment types, according to Boucher and Jarman (1977) are unconsolidated and consolidated aeolian sands, limestones and granites. Vegetation growing within granite and limestone sediments contains rich species richness and can be classified as freshwater marshes and salt marshes. Freshwater marshes are dominated by species such as *Phragmites australis* and *Typha capensis*, while salt marshes are dominated by *Salicornia spp.*, *Juncus kraussii*, *Bassia diffusa*, and *Spartina maritima* (O'Callaghan, 1994).

Figure 2. Geology of the Langebaan Lagoon (directly taken from Reaper, 1995)

Climate

The lagoon is situated in a region that has semi-arid to arid conditions and has a mean annual rainfall of about 260 mm. The lagoon is situated in a winter rainfall region where most rainfall occurs during the months from May to July. Southerly winds are the predominant winds found throughout the year and northerly winds may be found occurring during the months of May to August. The temperature may vary between a winter low of about 5⁰C to a summer high of about 35⁰C.

3.2 Mapping of Langebaan Lagoon

Estuarine habitats were mapped using aerial photographs obtained from National Geospatial Information (NGI) of South Africa. Orthorectified photographs for 2010 were used along with 2013 unrectified aerial photographs. The 2013 images had better colour distinction than the 2010 images and helped with the identification of habitat boundaries which did not appear to change much over the 3-year period. Submerged macrophyte habitat was based on the 2013 images as there appeared to be a large increase in area since 2010. In the southern section of the lagoon there is a large network of water channels within the salt marsh habitat. These were not mapped due to their small size. The vegetation map of Boucher and Jarman (1977) was used as a reference along with site photographs and cover data from 3 transects located within the Langebaan Lagoon that were assessed in 1977. Mapping was done at 1: 1 500 scale. The mosaic pattern of salt marsh distribution in the Langebaan Lagoon made mapping difficult in places but the broad habitats of open water, submerged macrophytes, intertidal salt marsh, intertidal-supratidal salt marsh mix, supratidal salt marsh, reeds and sedges were used, along with a separate mapping of *Juncus* habitat. Boucher and Jarman (1977) have this habitat intermingled with a terrestrial species, *Cliffortia strobilifera* in the south eastern section and distinction between the two was difficult. *Juncus* habitat might therefore be overestimated. Mapping was done within the 5 m contour line. The software used was ArcGis 10.2 (ESRI, Redlands, CA).

3.3 Species sampling

Transects were sampled during 22-28th March 2014, along a tidal inundation gradient from the water's edge to the terrestrial vegetation. A total of six transects were selected, each at a different site. Transects chosen were situated similarly to those of O'Callaghan (1994). Along each transects, vegetation cover was determined using a 1m² quadrat in replica, along every 5 m of the transect or every 1 m when there were obvious changes in species composition. The zones were identified by coarse changes in the species composition. Details of each transect is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: Description of transects

Transect	Description	Length
T1	Geelbek; 33 ⁰ 11'29.572"S, 18 ⁰ 07'27.020"E until 33 ⁰ 11'30.799"S, 18 ⁰ 07'35.99"E	390 m
T2	1 km southwest of transect 1; 33 ⁰ 11'37.787"S, 18 ⁰ 07'18.052"E	195 m
T3	14 km from Preekstoel; 33 ⁰ 09'06.507"S, 18 ⁰ 02'25.160."E and ending at 33 ⁰ 11'30.377"S, 18 ⁰ 07'33.887"E.	178 m
T4	Skrywershoek; 33 ⁰ 10'53.860"S, 18 ⁰ 04'33.254"E until 33 ⁰ 10'59.066"S, 18 ⁰ 04'32.590"E.	165 m
T5	Oosterval, no coordinates taken	120 m
T6	Southern shore, west of Geelbek; 33 ⁰ 12'46.796"S, 18 ⁰ 06'52.795"E until 33 ⁰ 12'39.064"S, 18 ⁰ 06'56.953"E	276 m

3.4 Sediment sampling

Sediment samples were collected in each of the different vegetation Zones. Within each Zone, three replicate samples, of approximately 400 g sediment each were collected. There will be a total of 82 sediment samples. Each sample was sealed and transported to the laboratory at NMMU for analysis of sediment moisture, redox potential, pH, organic matter and electrical conductivity.

Sediment moisture content

Moisture content was determined by weighing an amount of sediment sediment that was greater than the weight of the crucible. Sediment samples were weighed to an accuracy of 0.01 g. The crucibles were places in a drying oven for 48 hours at a temperature of 100⁰C. The samples were then weighed again. Before the moisture content was determined the original crucible weight was subtracted from the crucible wet weight and the crucible and dry weight. The moisture content was determined as follows:

$$\left(\frac{M_w - M_d}{M_w}\right) \times 100$$

M_w was the initial wet weight and M_d is the dry weight.

Sediment organic content

The sediment organic content was determined according to the method of Briggs (1977). Dried sediment samples were weighed in crucibles and put into an ashing oven for 12 hours at 550 °C. Once dried, the percentage organic matter was calculated using the following equation:

$$\left(\frac{M_d - M_a}{M_d}\right) \times 100$$

M_d was the initial dry mass and M_a is the mass after ashing.

Sediment electrical conductivity (EC)

Sediment electrical conductivity (mS.cm⁻¹) was determined as opposed to salinity. Air dried sediment samples were consisting of approximately 250 g were saturated with de-ionised water. The paste stood for an hour before being filtered using Whatman No. 40 filter paper. Conductivity was measured using a YSI 30M/10FT hand held conductivity meter. This procedure followed that of Barnard (1990).

Sediment pH

The method of measuring sediment pH was modified after Black (1965). Each sediment sample weighing about 5 g was placed in a 100 ml conical flask and to it 50 ml of distilled water was added. The sample was placed on a shaker for 30 minutes before the pH readings were taken. The pH readings were taken using a Beckman Φ 310 series

EDTA pH meter and probe. The pH meter was calibrated at 20 °C at a pH of 4, 7 and 10.

Sediment redox potential

The redox potential of the sediment was determined according to Barnard (1990). A Metrohm AG 9101 electrode attached to a Beckman Φ 310 series EDTA pH meter was calibrated with a Metrohm Standard redox solution at a potential of $U = + 250.5$ (mV) at a temperature of 20 °C. Distilled water (25 ml) was added to 12.5 g of sediment in a conical flask. The redox probe was inserted into the solution and shaken for 30 minutes and the reading taken.

Sediment particle size

The hydrometer method by Gee and Boudier, (1986) was used to determine the particle size of the sediment. Air dried sediment, weighing 40 g, was put into a beaker and to it, 100 ml of a 50 g l⁻¹ solution of sodium hexametaphosphate (NaPO₂) and 250 ml distilled water was added to each sample. The beakers were shaken mechanically for an hour before the analysis. The sediment mixture was then placed into a 1 L measuring cylinder and distilled water was added until the cylinder was full. The cylinder was closed and shaken for a minute by hand. Two drops of annyl alcohol was added to remove foam from the samples. A hydrometer was inserted after 30 seconds, 60 seconds, 3 minutes, 1.5 hours and 24 hours. A blank containing a similar solution without sediment was prepared. The readings were used in the following equations to calculate the percentage of size fractions of each sample.

The concentration (C) of sediment in suspension in g L⁻¹ was determined using:

$$C = R - RL$$

R is the uncorrected hydrometer reading and RL is the hydrometer reading of the blank.

The summary percentage (P) for the given time interval was determined using:

$$P < 0.05 \left(\frac{C}{C_0} \right) * 100$$

Co is the oven dried weight of the sample.

The mean particle diameter (X) in μm at time r was determined using:

$$X = \phi r^{-1/2}$$

ϕ is the sediment parameter ($\mu\text{m min}^{1/2}$) is a function of the hydrometer settling depth, solution viscosity and particle and solution density

$$\phi = \left(\frac{18 \eta h'}{[g(p_s - p_l)]^{1/2}} \right)$$

The hydrometer settling depth (cm) is h' , p_s = sediment particle density (g cm^3), p_l is the solution density (g cm^3), g is the gravitational constant (cm s^2) and η is the fluid viscosity in poise ($\text{g cm}^{-1} \text{s}^{-1}$).

The relationship of the settling depth to the hydrometer dimensions were approximated by:

$$h' = -0.164 R + 16.3$$

R is the uncorrected hydrometer reading.

The summation percentage was calculated using the following:

$$P_{2\mu m} = m \ln\left(\frac{2}{x_{24}}\right) + P_{24}$$

X_{24} is the mean particle diameter in suspension at 24 hours, P_{24} is the summation percentage at 24, and m was determined using the following equation:

$$m = \frac{P_{1.5} - P_{24}}{\ln(X_{1.5}) - X_{24}}$$

M is the slope of summation percentage curve between X at 1.5 hours and X at 24 hours. $X_{1.5}$ is the particle diameter in suspension at 1.5 hours and $P_{1.5}$ is the percentage at 1.5 hours. This procedure was repeated for the 30 second and 60 second readings.

Groundwater analysis

Depth to the water table and groundwater physiochemistry were measured within the different zones along each transect, to determine its influence on salt marsh vegetation. Replicate boreholes were hand augered to the depth to the water table. Once augered, the groundwater was allowed to stabilise, after which depth to the water table was

determined using a graduated stick. Groundwater electrical conductivity and salinity was measured using an YSI 30M/10FT hand held meter.

Statistical analysis

R Studio version 0.98.507 (2013) was used for statistical analysis. Normality of each environmental factor was tested by using the Shapiro-Wilks test in Stats Package (R Core Team, 2014).

The two-way ANOVA – Tukey Post Hoc HSD test was used to test for significance of parametric data and the Kruskal-Wallis test, using AgriColae 1.2-0 Statistical Procedures for agricultural Research Package (de Mendiburu, 2014), was used to testy significance for non-parametric data. The Spearman Correlation Test was used to test for correlation between each environmental factor using Corrgram Package (Wright, 2013).

Constraint Correspondence Analysis (CCA) and Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) of species and quadrat was performed to identify grouping in vegetation along transects as well as to determine the relationship between species and environmental variables, using Vegan Community Ecology Package (Oksanen *et al.*, 2013).

4. Results

4.1 Current vegetation distribution at Langebaan Lagoon

The distribution of the different plant communities are depicted in Fig. 3 and the study site areas are shown. The supratidal salt marsh and intertidal salt marsh were the dominant vegetation types each making up 23% of the vegetation, covering a total of about 524 ha (Table 3). *Juncus* patches covered 458.6 ha (21%) while reeds and sedge communities covered 123.6 ha (6%) (Table 3). The intertidal-supratidal mix community covered 267.7 ha (12%), the submerged macrophyte (*Zostera capensis*).

Table 3. Area (in hectares) covered by different plant communities at Langebaan Lagoon

Habitat types	Area (ha)	Percentage (%)
Development	99.1	-
Submerged macrophytes	85.8	4
Dune vegetation	38.2	2
Sand and beach	9.2	0
Unknown	38.6	2
<i>Juncus</i>	458.8	21
<i>Spartina</i>	163.4	7
Intertidal salt marsh	524.0	23
Intertidal-supratidal mix	267.7	12
Supratidal	523.7	23
Reeds and sedges	123.6	6
Water area	4017.1	-

Langebaan vegetation map

0 0.75 1.5 3 Kilometers

Coordinate System: WGS 1984 Transverse Mercator
Central Meridian: 19°00'E

Figure 3. Vegetation and habitat distribution at Langebaan Lagoon

4.2 Transect 1: Geelbeek

Figure 4 illustrates the percentage cover of plant species along the transect and the various zones can clearly be identified. This was a relatively long transect (390 m) containing 27 plant species and seven zones. Many species appeared to dominate at different distances along the transect (i.e. occupy greatest cover). Bare ground patches were scarce and were mainly found in the terrestrial zone. The first five meters (Zone 1) along the transect was at the water's edge and *Spartina maritima* and *Schoenoplectus triqueter* were the dominant species (Plate 1a). Zone 2 consisted of *Sarcocornia tegetaria*, *Bassia diffusa* and *Salicornia uniflora*, which were the most abundant species, some of these species may be seen in Plate 1a. This Zone occurred between 6 – 75 m along the transect. The vegetation changed to a different zone (Zone 4, between 105-180 m) that mainly consisted of *Sarcocornia tegetaria*. Zones 2 and 4 were separated by a patch of *Juncus kraussii* (Zone 3) at 80-95 m along the transect. Zone 5, found at 185-305 m along the transect, consisted of *Juncus kraussii* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* and Zone 6 consisted of *Juncus acutus* between 315-345 m along the transect (these patches may be seen in Plate 1b). The last Zone along this transect (Zone 7) consisted of *Juncus kraussii*, *Sporobolus virginicus* and *Chrysanthemoides monilifera*. The elevation gradually increased from the water edge to the last zone along the transect. The elevation at Zone 5 decreased slightly from 220 to 290 m before increasing. At Zone 2 and Zone 6, a formation of a pool or channel can be seen. The salt marsh species within the different zones along this transect displayed a mosaic pattern of distribution.

Figure 4. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 1.

Plate 1. Transect 1. (a) The start of the transect from the water edge, (b) the continuation from the transect into the *Juncus acutus* patch.

Sediment characteristics

The sediment moisture content was found to be significantly different along this transect ($H = 14.823$, d.f. = 6, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 5a). The highest sediment moisture content was recorded at Zone 6 (Zone 6 = 64.6%, S.E. = 14.3) and was significantly higher than at Zone 3 (Zone 3 = 44.6%, S.E. = 13.19, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 (Zone 7 = 11.3%, S.E. = 2.8, $p < 0.05$). The sediment moisture content was high (above 44% moisture) along the different Zones of the salt marsh between 5 - 315 m along the transect. At Zone 7 the lowest sediment moisture content was recorded (Zone 7 = 11.3%) and was significantly lower to the sediment moisture found at Zone 1 (Zone 1 = 58.8%, S.E. = 1.5, $p < 0.05$). The sediment moisture content decreased from Zone 1 to Zone 3 and increased until Zone 6, where the moisture content decreased to Zone 7.

The sediment organic content was found to have varied significantly along this transect ($H = 14.828$, d.f. = 6, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 5b). The sediment organic content at Zone 1 was significantly lower to the organic content at Zone 5 (Zone 5 = 23.4%, S.E. = 3.0, $p < 0.05$) and at Zone 6 (Zone 6 = 28.8%, S.E. = 2.2, $p < 0.05$). At 70 m a high organic matter content was found (Zone 2 = 36.8%, S.E. = 39.9). The lowest organic content was at Zone 7 (Zone 7 = 4.7%, S.E. = 1.5) and was significantly lower than the organic matter content at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 4 (Zone 4 = 19.2, S.E. = 3.1, $p < 0.05$), Zone 5 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$). The sediment organic content increased from Zone 3 to Zone 7 (Fig 5b) and it was found that Zone 6 was significantly higher in organic content to Zone 3 (Zone 3 = 10.6%, S.E. = 4.5, $p < 0.05$).

Sediment electrical conductivity was significantly different along this transect ($F = 21.16$, d.f. = 6, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 5c). The highest sediment electrical conductivity occurred at 205 m (Zone 4 = 89.0 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 9.7) and was significantly greater than all other Zones ($p < 0.05$). The lowest electrical conductivity was at 370 m (Zone 7 = 4.6 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 2.4) (Fig 5c). The electrical conductivity at Zone 7 was significantly lower than at 70 m (Zone 2 = 58.3, S.E. = 7.3, $p < 0.05$), 150 m (Zone 3 = 40.8 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 7.2, $p < 0.05$), 205 m (Zone 4 = 89.0 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 9.74, $p < 0.05$), 265 m (Zone 5 = 48.9 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 7.9, $p < 0.05$) and 315 m (Zone 6 = 46.1 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 15.8, $p < 0.05$). The electrical conductivity at Zone 2 was significantly greater than at 5 m (Zone 1 = 28.0 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 12.7, $p < 0.05$).

The pH values varied between the various salt marsh zones, with the lowest values occurring at 70 m (Zone 2 = 7.9, S.E. = 0.0) and at 370 m (Zone 7 = 7.9, S.E. = 0.2). The highest values occurred at 265 m (Zone 5 = 8.4, S.E. = 0.1) (Fig 5d). There was no significant differences between the zones ($p > 0.05$).

The sediment redox potential was significant along this transect ($H = 18.602$, d.f. = 6, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 5e). The most reduced sediment occurred at 70 m (Zone 2 = -41.0 mV, S.E. = 9.5) and was significantly more reduced than at 150 m (Zone 3 = 40.3 mV, S.E. = 7.8, $p < 0.05$), 205 m (Zone 4 = 51.3 mV, S.E. = 3.1, $p < 0.05$), 265 m (Zone 5 = 27.3 mV, S.E. = 2.5, $p < 0.05$) and 370 m (Zone 7 = 37.0 mV, S.E. = 8.2, $p < 0.05$). The redox potential at 5 m (Zone 1 = 22.7 mV, S.E. = 1.2) was significantly more reduced than at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$). The least reduced potential was at Zone 4 (51.3 mV) and was significantly less reduced than at Zone 5 ($p < 0.05$) and 315 m (Zone 6 = 20.7, S.E. = 4.2, $p < 0.05$). The redox potential at Zone 6 was significantly more reduced than at Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$) and significantly less reduced than at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

There were no significant differences between the silt, clay and sand compositions ($p > 0.05$) along the transect. The general trend of the particle size analysis data showed that sand content increased from the water edge at about 5 m (Zone 1 = 28%) to 150 m (Zone 3 = 46%) and then decreased until 370 m (Zone 7 = 15%). Silt composition increased along the transect from Zone 1 to Zone 7 and clay composition decreased along the transect from Zone 1 to Zone 7 (Fig 5f). Silt composition was greatest at 370 m (Zone 7 = 72%), while sand composition was greatest at 170 m (Zone 4 = 63%) and clay composition was lowest at Zone 7 (13%).

Figure 5. Sediment characteristics along Transect 1. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars = \pm S.E., n=3.

Groundwater characteristics

Groundwater electrical conductivity (Fig 6a) followed the same trend to that of groundwater salinity (Fig 6b). The groundwater electrical conductivity was significantly different along the transect ($H = 17.590$, d.f. = 6 $p < 0.05$). The lowest electrical conductivity occurred at 370 m (Zone 7 = 2.0 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 1.6) and was significantly lower than all other zones ($p < 0.05$). The highest electrical conductivity occurred at 265 m (Zone 5 = 69.5, S.E. = 1.3) and was significantly higher in electrical conductivity than at 5 m (Zone 1 = 49.8, S.E. = 0.7, $p < 0.05$), 70 m (Zone 2 = 52.8, S.E. = 14.0, $p < 0.05$), 205 m (Zone 4 = 41.4, S.E. = 3.7, $p < 0.05$), 315 m (Zone 6 = 12.7 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 8.7, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$). Groundwater electrical conductivity was significantly lower at Zone 1 than at Zone 5 ($p < 0.05$) and was significantly higher than at Zone 6, ($p < 0.05$). The electrical conductivity at Zone 2 was significantly lower than at Zone 5 and significantly higher than Zone 6 ($p < 0.05$). The Groundwater electrical conductivity was high throughout Zones 1 to 5 and decreased within zones 6 and 7.

The depth to the groundwater table varied significantly along the transect ($F = 30.14$, d.f. = 6, $p < 0.05$). The greatest depth to groundwater was at 370 m (Zone 7 = 97.0 cm, S.E. = 1.7) and was significantly greater than the depth to groundwater at 150 m (Zone 3 = 46.7 cm, S.E. = 11.6, $p = 0.05$), 205 m (Zone 4 = 43.3 cm, S.E. = 20.8, $p < 0.05$), 265 m (Zone 5 = 7.7 cm, S.E. = 2.5, $p < 0.05$) and at 315 m (Zone 6 = 65.0 cm, S.E. = 13.2, $p < 0.05$). The lowest depth to groundwater was at 5 m (Zone 1 = 0.0 cm, S.E. = 0.0) (Fig 6c). The depth to groundwater at 5 m was significantly lower to the depth to groundwater at 70 m (Zone 2 = 72.5 cm, S.E. = 3.5, $p < 0.05$), Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 6 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$). The depth to groundwater at Zone 5 was significantly lower than the depth to groundwater at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 6 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 7 ($p < 0.05$).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 6. Groundwater characteristics along Transect 1. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3

Habitat distribution

The vegetation was analysed with Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) (Fig 7). This transect was significantly affected by all the environmental factors ($p < 0.05$). There were three distinct communities identified: The intertidal salt marsh community, the supratidal salt marsh community and the terrestrial community. Species within the intertidal salt marsh include dominant species such as *Schoenoplectus triquetus* and *Spartina maritima* (indicated as green circle). The supratidal marsh includes dominant species such as *Juncus acutus*, *Juncus kraussii* and *Sarcocornia pillansii* (indicated as blue circle). The terrestrial zone (Zone 7) consisted of *Sporobolus virginicus* and *Chrysanthemoides monilifera* (indicated as red circle).

The intertidal salt marsh community occurred nearest to the water edge and was associated with a high percentage of clay (CA1 = -0.874, CA2 = 0.486, $r^2 = 0.682$, $p < 0.05$) and silt composition (CA1 = 0.725, CA2 = -0.689, $r^2 = 0.544$, $p < 0.05$), high groundwater electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.704, CA2 = 0.711, $r^2 = 0.433$, $p < 0.05$) and low elevation (CA1 = 0.680, CA2 = -0.733, $r^2 = 0.217$, $p < 0.05$).

The supratidal salt marsh community was associated with a high sediment moisture content (CA1 = -0.225, CA2 = 0.974, $r^2 = 0.719$, $p < 0.05$), a high sediment electrical conductivity (CA1 = 0.151, CA2 = 0.988, $r^2 = 0.308$, $p < 0.05$) and groundwater electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.704, CA2 = 0.711, $r^2 = 0.433$, $p < 0.05$), increased groundwater depth (CA1 = -0.093, CA2 = -0.9996, $r^2 = 0.237$, $p < 0.001$) and high pH (CA1 = -0.232, CA2 = 0.973, $r^2 = 0.346$, $p < 0.05$).

The terrestrial Zone was associated with an increase in depth to the groundwater table, a high elevation (CA1 = 0.890, CA2 = -0.455, $r^2 = 0.708$, $p < 0.05$), a low moisture content (CA1 = -0.225, CA2 = 0.974, $r^2 = 0.719$, $p < 0.05$), low organic content (CA1 = -0.016, CA2 = 1.00, $r^2 = 0.262$, $p < 0.05$), a high percentage of silt content (CA1 = 0.725, CA2 = -0.689, $r^2 = 0.544$, $p < 0.05$) and low groundwater salinity (CA1 = -0.707, CA2 = 0.708, $r^2 = 0.414$, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 7. CCA plot of species and environmental factors along Transect 1. Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.9251, 2=0.8703, 3=0.8653, 4=0.7901. Total inertia = 8.424., sum of eigenvalues = 3.086. GW = groundwater, Sed = Sediment.

4.3 Transect 2: Southwest of Geelbeek

The transect started at the water edge (Zone 1, 0 m) and ended in Zone 4 (190 m) (Plate 2a). The highest elevation (92.5 cm) occurred at 180 m (Fig 8). The dominant species for the first 35 m of along the transect (Zone 1) was *Spartina maritima* and *Triglochin buchenaui*. The vegetation changed to the dominant species being *Sporobolus fimbriatus*, *Bassia diffusa* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* in Zone 2 at 35 to 65 m along the transect. Zone 3 was found between 70 and 170 m consisting of *Sarcocornia pillansii* as the dominant species. The last Zone (Zone 4), between 170-190 m was dominated by *Sporobolus virginicus* and *Chrysanthemoides monilifera*. The elevation along this transect increased evenly until the end on Zone 3. A stream was situated between Zone 3 and Zone 4 (150 to 165 m), which resulted in the decrease in elevation that can be seen (Fig 8; Plate 2b). Only 17 plant species were found along this transect. *Sarcocornia pillansii* occurred at a much higher density within this transect to that of Transect 1 and the salt marsh zones were more distinct and displayed less of a mosaic pattern.

- | | | | |
|-------------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|-----------------------|
| Algae | Spartina maritima | Triglochin buchenau | Bassia diffusa |
| Limonium linifolium | Salicornia uniflora | Sarcocornia pillansii | Sporobolus virginicus |
| Limonium depauperatum | Sarcocornia tegetaria | Wrach | Disphyma crassifolium |
| Sporobolus fimbriatilis | Delosperma litorale | Atriplex cinerea | Atriplex semibaccata |
| Suaeda inflata | Cynodon dactylon | Bare | Water |
| Dead | Dry and bare | | |

Figure 8. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 2

Plate 2. Transect 2. (a) The transect within the intertidal zone. (b) A stream located in the supratidal zone.

Sediment characteristics

Sediment moisture content decreased along the transect from 10 m (Zone 1 = 61.8%, S.E. = 3.20) to 185 m (Zone 4 = 30.1%, S.E. = 38.2). The sediment moisture content was highest at Zone 1 and lowest at Zone 4 (Fig 9a). There was no significance between in sediment moisture along this transect ($p > 0.05$).

The sediment organic content was highest at 10 m (Zone 1=19.0%, S.E.=12.1) and decreased along the transect until 185 m (Zone 4 = 14.9%, S.E.=12.8) (Fig 9b). There was no significant difference in sediment organic content along this transect ($p > 0.05$).

The sediment electrical conductivity was highest at 60 m (Zone 2 = 47.9 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 10.05) and lowest at 105 m (Zone 3 = 32.3 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 11.5) (Fig 9c). The sediment electrical conductivity pattern was very similar to that of the percentage sediment moisture.

There was a significantly difference in pH along this transect ($F = 4.27$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The sediment pH was very similar throughout the transect. The highest pH occurred at 185 m (Zone 4 = 8.2, S.E.=0.3). The lowest pH occurred at 60 m (Zone 2 = 7.8, S.E. = 0.1) and was significantly lower in pH than at Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$) (Fig 9d). The pH at Zone 4 was significantly greater than the pH at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$).

Sediment redox potential was significantly different along the transect ($H = 9.619$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$ mV). The sediment redox potential increased along the transect from the water edge at 10 m (Zone 1 = -91.33 mV, S.E. = 50.93) to 185 m (Zone 4 = 51.33 mV, S.E. = 3.06) (Fig 9e). The sediment at Zone 1 was significantly less reduced than at 105 m (Zone 3 = 14.33, S.E. = 4.04 mV, $p < 0.05$) and at Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The sediment at 60 m (Zone 2 = 2.00, S.E.=18.68) was significantly more reduced than at Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$).

Sand and clay composition decreased along the transect, while silt composition increased along the transect from the water edge into Zone 4 (Fig 9f). There was a significant difference in clay composition along the transect ($F = 56.14$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The clay composition at 10 m (Zone 1 = 39.4%) was significantly greater than at

105 m (Zone 3 = 29.0%) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The clay composition at 60 m (Zone 2 = 37.2%) was significantly greater than at Zone 3 and Zone 4.

Figure 9. Sediment characteristics along Transect 2. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars =±S.E., n=3

Groundwater characteristics

Groundwater salinity decreased along the transect from 33 ppt at 10 m (Zone 1) to 4.72 ppt at 185 m (Zone 4) (Fig 10a). The groundwater conductivity followed the same trend as the groundwater salinity. The highest conductivity occurred at a distance of 10 m (Zone 1 = 50.2 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 0.8) and the lowest value occurred at a distance of 185 m (Zone 4 = 8.3 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 5.5) (Fig 10b). The groundwater electrical conductivity / salinity at 10 m (Zone 1) was significantly higher than at 185 m (Zone 4, $H = 7.106$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$).

The depth to the groundwater table was significant along this transect ($F = 115.4$ cm, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The depth was greatest at 185 m (Zone 4 = 135.0 cm, S.E. = 7.1) (Fig 10c). The depth to groundwater at 185 m was significantly greater to the depth at 10 m (Zone 1 = 0.00 cm, S.E. = 0.00, $p < 0.05$), 60 m (Zone 2 = 98.7 cm, S.E. = 1.2, $p < 0.05$) and 105 m (Zone 3 = 76.67 cm, S.E. = 15.27, $p < 0.001$). The lowest depth to groundwater at 10 m (Zone 1) was significantly lower to the depth at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The depth to groundwater along this transect showed an increasing trend from Zone 1 to Zone 4.

Figure 10. Groundwater characteristics along Transect 2. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3

Habitat distribution

The Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showed that, other than sediment organic content, the vegetation distribution along Transect 2 was significantly affected by all other environmental factors ($p < 0.05$). There were two main communities identified: The intertidal salt marsh community (green circle) and the supratidal salt marsh community (purple circle) (Fig 11).

The intertidal salt marsh community included dominant species such as *Spartina maritima*, *Bassia diffusa* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* (Fig 11). This community was associated with shallow depth to the groundwater table (CA1 = 0.973, CA2 = -0.230, $r^2 = 0.426$, $p < 0.05$), and high sediment electrical conductivity / salinity (CA1 = -0.796, CA2 = 0.605, $r^2 = 0.507$, $p < 0.05$), high sand (CA1 = -0.574, CA2 = 0.819, $r^2 = 0.411$, $p < 0.05$) and clay (CA1 = -0.770, CA2 = 0.638, $r^2 = 0.777$, $p < 0.05$) sediment composition and high sediment moisture content (CA1 = -0.784, CA2 = 0.620, $r^2 = 0.842$, $p < 0.05$).

The supratidal salt marsh community included species such as *Limonium depauperatum* and *Sarcocornia pillansii* was associated with increased elevation (CA1 = 0.890, CA2 = -0.455, $r^2 = 0.708$, $p < 0.05$), greater groundwater depth (CA1 = 0.973, CA2 = -0.229, $r^2 = 0.426$, $p < 0.05$), high sediment redox potential (CA1 = 0.924, CA2 = -0.383, $r^2 = 0.642$, $p < 0.05$), sediment alkalinity (CA1 = 0.520, CA2 = -0.854, $r^2 = 0.594$, $p < 0.05$), high silt composition (CA1 = 0.724, CA2 = -0.700, $r^2 = 0.678$, $p < 0.05$) and low groundwater electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.7924, CA2 = 0.611, $r^2 = 0.489$, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 11. CCA plot of species and environmental factors along Transect 2. Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.959, 2=0.811, 3=0.733, 4=0.623. Total inertia = 6.722. GW = groundwater, Sed = Sediment.

4.4 Transect 3: Preekstoel

There were four distinct zones that could be seen along Transect 3. The first Zone occurred between 0 to 23 m and included the water edge (Fig 12, Plate 3). At this Zone the dominant plant species was *Spartina maritima*. At Zone 2, between 23 and 45 m, the elevation increased as this zone was situated on a small sand dune (Plate 3). The dominant species were *Bassia diffusa*, *Sarcocornia tegetaria* and *Tetragonia fruticosa*. At Zone 3 the elevation decreased and remained relatively level up until 170 m (Zone 4) (Fig 12). Zone 3 was dominated by *Sarcocornia tegetaria*, *Triglochin buchenau* and *Tetragonia fruticosa*. Zone 4 was situated between 170 to 185 m and was dominated by *Atriplex semibaccata*. The salt marsh vegetation at Zone 3 was seen to occur in a mosaic pattern, similarly to that observed at Transect 1.

Figure 12. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 3.

Plate 3. Transect 3. (a) The start of the transect at the water edge. (b) Part of the transect from the sand dune into the supratidal zone.

Sediment characteristics

The sediment moisture content varied along the transect (Fig 13a). The highest sediment moisture content was at 90 m (Zone 3 = 59.4%, S.E. = 17.1). The lowest sediment moisture content occurred at 32 m (Zone 2 = 2.50%, S.E. = 0.53). There was no significant difference between sediment moisture within the various zones along this transect ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment organic content followed a similar trend to that of sediment moisture content (Fig 13b). The sediment organic content was greatest at 90 m (Zone 3 = 21.2%, S.E. = 13.9). The lowest organic content occurred on the dune patch at 32 m (Zone 2 = 1.0%, S.E. = 0.2). There was no significant difference between sediment organic content within the various zones along this transect ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment electrical conductivity varied along the transect and was found to be significantly different ($H = 9.390$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest electrical conductivity occurred at 90 m (Zone 3 = 46.2 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 4.5) and was significantly greater than at 32 m (Zone 2 = 2.9 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 2.9, $p < 0.05$) and at 174 m (Zone 4 = 4.5 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 5.8, $p < 0.05$). The lowest electrical conductivity occurred within the sand dune region at Zone 2 (Fig 13c). The electrical conductivity at 10 m (Zone 1 = 29.3 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 8.4) was significantly greater than the electrical conductivity at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$). There was no sediment electrical conductivity trend observed within this transect.

Sediment pH was significantly different along this transect ($F = 37.81$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The greatest pH value was at 32 m (Zone 2 = 9.2, S.E. = 0.2) and was significantly greater than the pH at 10 m (Zone 1 = 8.5, S.E. = 0.1, $p < 0.05$). This Zone was a small sand dune. The lowest pH value occurred at 90 m (Zone 3 = 7.4, S.E. = 0.3) (Fig 13d). The pH at Zone 3 was significantly lower than the pH at Zone (p < 0.05), Zone 2 (p < 0.05) and at 174 m (Zone 4 = 8.7, S.E. = 0.3, $p < 0.05$).

The lowest reduced sediment occurred at 90 m (Zone 3 = 24.7 mV, S.E. = 6.8) (Fig 13e). The redox potential at Zone 3 was significantly greater than the redox potential at 32 m (Zone 2 = -2.0 mV, S.E. = 1.7, $p < 0.05$) The most reduced sediment conditions were within the sand dune at 32 m (Zone 2 = -2.0 mV, S.E. = 1.7) and the sediment was significantly more reduced than at 174 m (Zone 4 = 23.3 mV, S.E. = 10.7, $p < 0.05$). This

transect had reduced sediment conditions and was most reduced within Zone 1 and 2 (Fig 13e).

Sand and clay compositions were greatest at 90 m (Zone 3) (Fig 13f). Clay made up 30%, while Sand made up 39.2% of the sediment composition at Transect 3. Silt content was high at all other zones (greater than 60%). Clay and silt sediment compositions were significantly different along this transect ($H > 10.3$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The greatest silt content was at a distance of 32 m (Zone 2 = 71.9%), and was significantly greater than at 90 m (Zone 3 = 30.8%) and 174 m (Zone 4 = 61.7%) ($p < 0.05$) (Fig 13f). The lowest clay composition was at 10 m (Zone 1 = 9.5%) and was significantly lower than at Zone 3 and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). Silt composition was highest at Zone 1 (65.5%) and was significantly greater than at Zone 3 (30.8%) and Zone 4 (61.7%) ($p < 0.05$). The silt content at Zone 2 (71.9) was also significantly greater than Zone 3 and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The silt composition at Zone 4 was also significantly greater than at Zone 3.

Figure 13: Sediment characteristics along Transect 3. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars = \pm S.E., n=3.

Groundwater characteristics

Groundwater salinity was significant along this transect ($F = 42.09$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 14a). Salinity was greatest at 174 m (Zone 4 = 41.7 $p < 0.05$, S.E.=6.6). The salinity at Zone 4 was significantly higher than at 32 m (Zone 2 = 11.4 $p < 0.05$, S.E. = 0.9, $p < 0.05$) and 90 m (Zone 3 = 29.1, S.E. = 3.9, $p < 0.05$). The groundwater salinity was significantly lower at 32 m (Zone 2) than at 10 m (Zone 1 = 35.4 $p < 0.05$, S.E. = 0.1, $p < 0.001$) and Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

The groundwater electrical conductivity (Fig 14b) was very similar in trend as groundwater salinity (Fig 14a). Electrical conductivity was significant along this transect ($F = 47.33$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest electrical conductivity was at 174 m (Zone 4 = 61.8 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 8.7). The electrical conductivity at Zone 4 was significantly higher than at 32 m (Zone 2 = 18.8 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 1.4, $p < 0.05$) and 90 m (Zone 3 = 44.9 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 5.4, $p < 0.05$). The lowest electrical conductivity reading was at 32 m (Zone 2 = 18.8 mS cm^{-1}) and was significantly lower than at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$). The electrical conductivity at Zone 4 was significantly higher than at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$).

The depth to the groundwater table displayed no trend along the transect, but was significantly different along the transect ($H = 8.530$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The depth was greatest in the highest Zone at 174 m (Zone 4 = 87.5 cm, S.E. = 3.5) and was significantly greater than at 10 m (Zone 1 = 0.0 cm, S.E. = 0.0, $p < 0.05$) (Fig 14c). The sand dune region at 32 m (Zone 2 = 86.67 cm, S.E. = 7.64) also had a high depth to groundwater and was significantly lower than at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$) (Fig 14c).

Figure 14. Groundwater characteristics along Transect 3. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3.

Habitat distribution

The Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showed that the vegetation distribution along Transect 2 was affected by all environmental factors ($p < 0.05$) except elevation ($p > 0.05$) (Fig 15). Three communities were identified along this transect. The intertidal salt marsh community (red circle), the intertidal - supratidal community (green circle) and the supratidal community (purple circle).

The intertidal community contains dominant species such as *Salicornia meyeriana* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* and is influenced by sediment organic matter (CA1 = -0.380, CA2 = 0.925, $r^2 = 0.722$), moisture content (CA1 = -0.530, CA2 = 0.848, $r^2 = 0.719$), sand particles (CA = -0.3067, CA2 = 0.952, $r^2 = 0.703$) clay particles (CA1 = -0.391, CA2 = 0.920, $r^2 = 0.723$), and groundwater salinity / electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.614, CA2 = 0.790, $r^2 = 0.669$).

The intertidal – supratidal community contained the dominant species *Spartina maritima* and *Sporobolus virginicus* and the community was influenced by alkaline sediment (CA1 = 0.376, CA2 = -0.926, $r^2 = 0.690$), increased depth to groundwater table (CA1 = 0.780, CA2 = -0.625, $r^2 = 0.510$) and high percentage silt particles (CA1 = 0.362, CA2 = -0.932, $r^2 = 0.718$).

The supratidal community had *Sarcocornia pillansii* and *Atriplex semibaccata* and was influenced by increased redox potential (CA1 = 0.112, CA2 = 0.994, $r^2 = 0.694$).

Figure 15. CCA plot of species and environmental factors along Transect 3. Eigenvalues axis 1=0.945, 2=0.881, 3=0.784, 4=0.759. Total inertia = 5.008. GW = groundwater, Sed = Sediment.

4.5 Transect 4: Skrywershoek

Zone 1 was situated between 0 to 60 m along Transect 4, which starting at the water edge (Fig 16). The dominant plant species occurring in Zone 1 was *Bassia diffusa*. Zone 2 was situated between 65 to 155 m and was dominated by *Sarcocornia tegetaria*. Zone 3 was situated between 160 – 170 m and was dominated by *Disphyma crassifolia*. The elevation along the transect varied throughout this transect. Many water pools were found along the transect, contributing to the elevation pattern that is observed. The salt marsh vegetation at Transect 4 was distributed in a mosaic manner (Plate 4).

Figure 16. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 4.

Plate 4. Transect 4 from the water edge to the mosaic patterned supratidal zone.

Sediment characteristics

The sediment moisture content increased from 25 m (Zone 1 = 9.76%, S.E. = 1.4) to 120 m (Zone 2 = 37.0%, S.E. = 1.3) and decreased at 162 m (Zone 3 = 8.8%, S.E. = 0.4) (Fig 17a). The greatest sediment moisture content occurred at Zone 2 (37.0%). The moisture content at Zone 2 was significantly higher to the moisture content at 162 m (Zone 3, $p < 0.05$).

The sediment organic content (Fig 17b) was significant along this transect ($H = 7.2$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The highest organic content was at 25 m (Zone 1 = 10.2%, S.E. = 2.6) and was found to have been significantly less than the organic content at 120 m (Zone 2 = 10.2%, S.E. = 0.7, $p < 0.05$) and 162 m (Zone 3 = 3.9%, S.E. = 0.8, $p < 0.05$). The organic content at 120 m (Zone 2) was significantly greater to the organic content at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

The highest sediment electrical conductivity was at 120 m (Zone 2 = 20.3 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 12.3). The lowest electrical conductivity was at 165 m (Zone 3 = 11.0 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 4.5) (Fig 17c). Sediment electrical conductivity was not significantly different between the various zones along the transect.

The pH was significant along this transect ($F = 42$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The highest pH values occurred at 162 m (Zone 3 = 8.8, S.E. = 0.3) and was significantly greater than the pH at 25 m (Zone 1 = 7.8, S.E. = 0.43, $p < 0.05$) and 120 m (Zone 2 = 6.3, S.E. = 0.3, $p < 0.05$). The lowest pH value occurred at Zone (6.3) (Fig 17d) and was significantly lower to the pH at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment redox potential was significantly different along this transect ($F = 109.2$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The least reducing sediment was at 120 m (Zone 2 = 86.0 mV, S.E. = 4.0) (Fig 17e). The sediment at Zone 2 was significantly less reduced than at 25 m (Zone 1 = 61.0 mV, S.E. = 8.5, $p < 0.05$) and 162 m (Zone 3 = 10.7 mV, S.E. = 5.7, $p < 0.1$). The sediment redox potential was lowest at Zone 31 (10.7 mV) (Fig 17e). The sediment at 162 m was significantly more reduced at Zone 3 compared to Zone 1 ($p < 0.1$) and Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$).

No silt particles were seen at 120 m (Zone 2), while at 25 m (Zone 1) and 162 m (Zone 3) had silt particles (Fig 17f). No trend was observed for the various sediment

compositions (i.e. sand, silt and clay) (Fig 17f). The sand composition varied significantly along the transect ($F = 12.7$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The most sand composition was at Zone 2 (55.7%) and it was significantly greater than at the other zones ($p < 0.05$). Clay composition also varied significantly along the transect ($H = 6.7126$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The clay composition was greatest at Zone 2 (58.6%) and was significantly greater than at Zone 3 (10.7%).

Figure 17. Sediment characteristics along Transect 4. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars = \pm S.E., n=3.

Groundwater characteristics

The groundwater salinity (Fig 18a) and groundwater electrical conductivity (Fig 18b) increased along the transect from 25 m (Zone 1 = 26.6 ppt, S.E. = 13.7) to 120 m (Zone 2 = 40.7 ppt, S.E. = 7.6) (Fig 18a) and decreased slightly from Zone 2 to 162 m (Zone 3 = 34.1 ppt, S.E. = 22.2) (Fig 18b). Groundwater salinity was not significantly different along this transect ($p < 0.05$).

Depth to groundwater was significantly different along this zone ($F = 24.5$, d.f. = 2, $p < 0.05$). The depth to the groundwater table was greatest at 162 m (Zone 3 = 100.0 cm, S.E. = 10.0). The lowest depth to the groundwater table was at 120 m (Zone 2 = 51.7 cm, S.E. = 2.9) in Zone 2 (Fig 18c). Zone 2 was significantly lower in depth to groundwater than the other zones ($p < 0.05$) and the depth at Zone 3 was significantly more higher than the other zones ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 18. Groundwater characteristics along transect 3. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3.

Habitat distribution

Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) showed that the vegetation distribution along transect 2 was affected by all environmental factors ($p < 0.05$) except elevation ($p > 0.05$). There were two communities identified along this transect: Intertidal community and the supratidal community (Fig 19).

The intertidal community contained dominant species such as *Spartina maritima* and *Sarcocornia tegeteria*. Environmental factors influencing this community were redox potential (CA1 = -0.653, CA2 = -0.758, $r^2 = 0.447$), sediment moisture content (CA1 = -0.902, CA2 = -0.433, $r^2 = 0.918$), sediment organic content (CA1 = -0.925, CA2 = -0.379, $r^2 = 0.950$), sediment electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.864, CA2 = -0.504, $r^2 = 0.849$), groundwater electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.957, CA2 = -0.290, $r^2 = 9.67$) / salinity (CA1 = -0.961, CA2 = -0.278, $r^2 = 9.966$), high sand content (CA1 = -0.920, CA2 = -0.392, $r^2 = 0.944$) and high clay content (CA1 = -0.896, CA2 = -0.445, $r^2 = 0.908$).

The supratidal community contained *Bassia diffusa* and *Sarcocornia pillansii* as dominant species and the environmental factors influencing this community was pH (CA1 = 0.814, CA2 = 0.580, $r^2 = 0.747$) and depth to the groundwater table (CA1 = 0.724, CA2 = 0.690, $r^2 = 0.566$).

All environmental factors influenced the salt marsh plant distribution ($p < 0.001$), including sediment moisture content (CA1=-0.987, CA2= 0.160, $r^2= 0.939$), Sediment organic content (CA1=-0.988, CA2=0.154, $r^2= 0.9656$), sediment electrical conductivity (CA1= -0.986, CA2= 0.168, $r^2= 0.8776$), pH (CA1=0.984, CA2= -0.179, $r^2=0.781$), pH (CA1= 0.984, CA2=-0.179, $r^2= 0.781$), sediment redox potential (CA1=-0.978, CA2= 0.211, $r^2= 0.473$), groundwater salinity / groundwater electrical conductivity (CA1=-0.989, CA2= 0.145, $r^2= 0.974$), depth to groundwater (CA1=0.98049, CA2=-0.197, $r^2= 0.600$) and sediment particles including sand (CA1=-0.988, CA2=0.156, $r^2= 0.961$), silt (CA1=0.987, CA2=-0.159, $r^2= 0.946$) and clay (CA1=-0.987, CA2= 0.162, $r^2= 0.931$).

Figure 19. : DCA plot of species and environmental factors along transect 3. Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.936, 2=0.759, 3=0.383, 4=0.356. Total inertia = 3.392. GW = groundwater, Sed = Sediment.

4.6 Transect 5: Oosterval

Transect 5 was situated near Oosterval. The dominant species at 0 to 15 m (zone 1) was *Spartina maritima*. Zone 2 was situated at 20 to 37 m and was dominated by *Spartina maritima* and *Limonium linifolium*. Zone 3 occurred between 40 and 90 m and was dominated by *Sarcocornia tegetaria*. The last zone, Zone 4 contained *Sarcocornia pillansii*, *Salvia africana-lutea* and *Ruschia tecta*. An increase in elevation can be seen before the start of each Zone (Fig 20). This elevation pattern was the most gradual and non-variable in comparison to the other transects and the vegetation composition changed suddenly as seen in Plate 5. The elevation at zone 2, between 20 and 80 m remained constant. Only nine species were identified along this transect.

- Bare
- Spartina maritima*
- bare and water
- Limonium linifolium*
- Sarcocornia tegetaria*
- Bassia diffusa*
- Triglochin buchenaui*
- Sarcocornia pillansii*
- Dead grass
- Sporobolus virginicus*
- Ruschia tecta*
- Salvia africana-lutea*

Figure 20. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 5.

Plate 5. Transect 5. (a) The transect starting from the water edge into the intertidal and supratidal zones. (b) The intertidal and supratidal zones displayed along the transect.

Sediment characteristics

The sediment moisture content was significant along this transect ($F = 9.94$, $d.f. = 3$, $p < 0.05$). The moisture content was greatest at 32 m (Zone 2 = 33.5%, S.E. = 10.1) moisture content) and the lowest sediment moisture content occurred at 110 m (Zone 4 = 6.1%, S.E. = 4.4) (Fig 21a). The moisture content at 32 m (Zone 2) was significantly greater than the moisture content at 70 m (Zone 3 = 15.0%, S.E. = 4.9, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment organic content increased from 10 m (Zone 1 = 1.0%, S.E. = 0.37) to 70 m (Zone 3 = 9.1%, S.E. = 5.3) and then decreased to 110 m (Zone 4 = 2.9%, S.E. = 0.4) (Fig 21b). The highest sediment organic content was at 70 m (Zone 3 = 9.1%) and was significantly greater than the organic content at 10 m (Zone 1 = 1.0%, $p < 0.05$). The lowest organic content was observed at Zone 4 (2.9%) (Fig 21b).

The sediment electrical conductivity was significantly different along this transect ($F = 35.6$, $d.f. = 3$, $p < 0.05$). The greatest electrical conductivity was at 32 m (Zone 2 = 51.3 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 2.64) and was significantly greater than the electrical conductivity at 10 m (Zone 1 = 31.5 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 11.3, $p < 0.05$), 70 m (Zone 3 = 12.3 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 5.3, $p < 0.05$) and 110 m (Zone 4 = 1.3 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 0.4, $p < 0.05$). The lowest electrical conductivity recorded was at Zone 4 (1.3 mS cm^{-1}) (Fig 21c). The electrical conductivity at Zone 4 was significantly lower than at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$) and at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$). The electrical conductivity at Zone 1 was significantly greater than the electrical conductivity at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$). The trend of sediment electrical conductivity was similar to that of the sediment moisture content.

Sediment pH was significantly different along this transect ($F = 11.7$, $d.f. = 3$, $p < 0.05$). The greatest pH was at 110 m (Zone 4 = 8.7, S.E. = 0.2) and is considered to be significantly different to the pH at 10 m (Zone 1 = 8.0, S.E. = 0.1, $p < 0.05$) and at 32 m (Zone 2 = 7.8, S.E. = 0.1, $p < 0.05$). The lowest pH was at Zone 2 (7.8) (Fig 21d). The pH at Zone 2 was significantly lower to the pH at 70 m (Zone 3 = 8.5, S.E. = 0.4, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment was least reduced at 10 m (Zone 1 = 63.0 mV, S.E. = 12.1). The most reduced sediment occurred at 70 m (Zone 3 = 40.3 mV, S.E. = 15.3) (Fig 21e). The sediment from Zone 1 to Zone 3 tended towards being more reduced and sediment at

Zone 1 was less reduced than at 110 m (Zone 4 = 49.7 mV, S.E. = 3.2). Sediment redox potential was not significantly different between the various zones along the transect ($p > 0.05$).

The sediment particle composition showed no trend along the transect. Sand composition was significantly different along the transect ($H = 9.274$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest sand composition was at 32 m (Zone 2 = 36.0%) was significantly greater to the sand composition at 10 m, which contained lowest sand composition (Zone 1 = 9.5%, $p < 0.05$). The silt composition had an opposite trend to the sand composition. Zone 1 contained the highest percentage of silt composition (79.7%) and was significantly greater than the silt composition at Zone 2 (47.5%). The clay content at 10 m was low (Zone 1 = 11%) a low clay content and a high silt content was observed. Clay and sand particles were greatest at 32 m (Zone 2 = 17.0%) The Zones 3 and 4 were similar in sediment particle types (high silt content) (Fig 21f).

(a)

(d)

(b)

(e)

(c)

(f)

Figure 21. Sediment characteristics along Transect 5. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars = \pm S.E., n=3.

Groundwater characteristics

There was a definite trend that can be observed with the groundwater characteristics. Groundwater salinity was significantly different along this transect ($H = 10.38$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The groundwater salinity decreased from 10 m (Zone 1 = 36.0 ppt, S.E. = 0.3) to 110 m (Zone 4 = 4.4 ppt, S.E. = 1.5) (Fig 22a). The salinity at Zone 1 was the highest along this transect and was significantly greater to the salinity at 32 m (Zone 2 = 18.1 ppt, S.E. = 1.9, $p < 0.05$), 70 m (Zone 3 = 9.1 ppt, $p < 0.05$, S.E. = 1.3, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4. ($p < 0.05$). The lowest salinity value was at Zone 4 (4.4 ppt) and was significantly lower than at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$). The salinity at Zone 2 was significantly greater than the salinity at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and significantly greater than the salinity at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$).

The groundwater electrical conductivity was similar to the salinity data. Groundwater electrical conductivity was significantly different along this transect ($F = 265$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest electrical conductivity value was at 10 m (Zone 1 = 54.4 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 0.4) and the lowest was at 110 m (Zone 4 = 7.9 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 2.6) (Fig 22b). Electrical conductivity at Zone 1 was significantly greater than at all other Zones ($p < 0.05$). Zone 2 was significantly greater in electrical conductivity than Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). Zone 4 was significantly lower in electrical conductivity than all the other zones ($p < 0.05$).

The depth to the groundwater table varied significantly along this transect ($F = 25.55$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The depth decreased from 110 m (Zone 4) to 10 m (Zone 1) (Fig 22c). The depth to the groundwater table was greatest at Zone 4 (115.0 cm, S.E. = 13.2) and was significantly greater than the depth at Zone 1 (0.0 cm, S.E. = 0.0, $p < 0.05$) and at 32 m (Zone 2 = 38.9 cm, S.E. = 29.3, $p < 0.05$). The depth to groundwater at Zone 1 was significantly lower to the depth at 70 m (Zone 3 = 85.0 cm, S.E. = 13.2, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$).

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure 22. Groundwater characteristics along Transect 5. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3.

Habitat distribution

The vegetation was analysed with Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) (Fig 23). The Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showed that the vegetation distribution along transect 5 was affected by all environmental factors except elevation ($p < 0.05$). There were three distinct community types that could be seen: The water edge, comprising only of *Spartina maritima*, the intertidal community (purple circle) and the supratidal community (green circle).

The water edge was affected by sediment moisture (CA1= -0.132, CA2 = -0.991, $r^2 = 0.453$), sediment electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.445, CA2 = -0.895, $r^2 = 0.475$), groundwater salinity (CA1 = -0.921, CA2 = -0.391, $r^2=0.260$) and electrical conductivity (CA1 = -0.905, CA2 = -0.426, $r^2 = 0.257$), sand particles (CA1 = 0.301, CA2 = -0.954, $r^2=0.287$) and clay particles (CA1 = -0.010, CA2 = -0.99995, $r^2 = 0.306$).

The intertidal community was dominated by *Triglochin buchinaui* and *Bassia diffusa* and the community was affected by high pH (CA1 = 0.508, CA2 = 0.861, $r^2 = 0.449$), increased organic matter (CA1 = 0.99989, CA2 = 0.015, $r^2 = 0.820$) and increased depth to groundwater (CA1 = 0.741, CA2 = 0.671, $r^2 = 0.277$).

The supratidal community contained *Sarcocornia pillansii* and *Sporobolus virginicus* as dominant species and is affected by increase in redox (CA1 = -0.997, CA2 = -0.083, $r^2 = 0.686$), a high silt content (CA1 = -0.316, CA2 = 0.949, $r^2 = 0.296$), high groundwater salinity (CA1 = -0.921, CA2 = -0.391, $r^2=0.260$) and high depth to groundwater (CA1 = 0.741, CA2 = 0.671, $r^2 = 0.277$).

Figure 23: CCA plot of species and environmental factors along Transect 5. Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.915, 2=0.803, 3=0.648, 4=0.534. Total inertia = 3.924. GW = groundwater, Sed = Sediment.

4.7 Transect 6: Southern Shore, west of Geelbeck

Transect 6 started at the water edge in a tidal channel. Zone 1 was situated between 0 and 40 m along the transect and was dominated by *Spartina maritima* and *Sarcocornia pillansii* (Fig 24). *Sarcocornia tegetaria* and *Triglochin buchenau* dominated Zone 2 at 45 to 140 m along the transect. The elevation along Zones 1 and 2 increased in a consistent manner up until approximately 105 m along the transect. The elevation thereafter decreased between 115 and 150 m and between 170 and 195 m along the transect. Zone 3 was positioned between 145 and 266 m along the transect and the dominant plant species were *Sarcocornia pillansii* and *Bassia diffusa*. The last Zone (Zone 4) was dominated by *Sarcocornia tegetaria* and *Salicornia meyeriana* and was situated between 266 and 276 m along the transect. Plate 6 shows the vegetation changed along the transect where there were differences in elevation.

- *Atriplex cinerea*
- *Spartina maritima*
- *Atriplex semibaccata*
- *Sarcocornia pillansii*
- *Lycium cinereum*
- Bare
- *sporobolous virginicus*
- *Bassia diffusa*
- *Limonium linifolium*
- *Sarcocornia tegetaria*
- *Salicornia meyeriana*
- *Triglochin buchenau*
- Mud
- Dead algae
- *Drosanthemum floribundum*
- Water and algae
- Water and bare

Figure 24. Species distribution and elevation along Transect 6.

Plate 6. Transect 6 (a) Areas that changed in elevation along the transect changed in species composition. (b) Areas without elevation contained an even distribution of species.

Sediment characteristics

The sediment moisture content was significant along this transect ($H = 9.974$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The sediment moisture content was greatest at 150 m (Zone 3 = 67.6%, S.E. = 2.0). The lowest sediment moisture was at 15 m (Zone 1 = 17.8%, S.E. = 1.4) (Fig 25a). The moisture content at Zone 1 was significantly different to the moisture content at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and 274 m (Zone 4 = 35.1%, S.E. = 1.7, $p < 0.05$). The moisture content at Zone 3 was significantly greater than the salinity at 90 m (Zone 2 = 19.9%, S.E. = 1.9, $p < 0.05$).

The sediment organic content was significant along this transect ($H = 9.67$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest sediment organic content was at 150 m (Zone 3 = 20.9%, S.E. = 1.6) (Fig 25b). The lowest organic content was at 274 m (Zone 4 = 7.1%, S.E. = 0.8) (Fig 25b). The organic content at Zone 3 was significantly greater than at 15 m (Zone 1 = 8.1%, S.E. = 0.7, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The organic content at Zone 4 was significantly less than at 90 m (Zone 2 = 9.8%, S.E. = 1.4, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

Sediment electrical conductivity was significant along this transect ($H = 10.4$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest recorded electrical conductivity value was at 150 m (Zone 3 = 70.7 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 6.2) and the lowest value was at 15m (Zone 1 = 1.4 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 0.7) (Fig 25c). The electrical conductivity at Zone 1 was significantly less than at 90 m (Zone 2 = 2.9 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 0.70, $p < 0.05$), Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and 274 m (Zone 4 = 28.9 mS cm^{-1} , S.E. = 0.95). The electrical conductivity at Zone 2 was significantly lower than at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). Zone 4 was significantly higher in terms of electrical conductivity than Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

The pH along this transect was significant ($F = 19.38$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest pH value recorded was at 15 m (Zone 1 = 8.1, S.E. = 0.2) and the lowest pH recorded was at 90 m (Zone 2 = 6.6, S.E. = 0.3) (Fig 25d). Zone 1 was significantly greater in salinity than Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$), 150 m (Zone 3 = 7.0, S.E. = 0.3, $p < 0.05$) and 274 m (Zone 4 = 6.6, S.E. = 0.4, $p < 0.05$).

The sediment redox potential was significant along this transect ($H = 8.077$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The least reduced sediment was at 90m (Zone 2 = 80.7 mS, S.E. = 5.5). The

most reduced sediment was at 150 m (Zone 3 = -64.0 mS, S.E. = 54.7) (Fig 25e). Zone 2 was significantly less reduced compared to Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

The sediment particle types varied throughout the transect. No silt was found occurring at 90 m (Zone 2) or at 274 m (Zone 4) (Fig 25f). The clay content varied throughout the different Zones and was greatest in Zone 4 (Fig 25f). The silt content varied significantly throughout the transect ($H = 9.27$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest silt content occurred at 15 m (Zone 1 = 26.9%) and was significantly more than the silt content at Zone 2 and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The silt content at 150 m (Zone 3 = 24.2%) was also significantly greater than at Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The clay content was significantly different along this transect ($H = 10.389$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest clay content occurred at Zone 4 (89.7%) and was significantly greater than at Zone 1 and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The clay content at Zone 2 was also high (74.6%) and was considered to be significantly greater than the clay content at Zone 3 and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 25: Sediment characteristics along Transect 6. Moisture content =a, organic content =b, electrical conductivity =c, pH= d, redox potential =e, particle types =f. Vertical bars = \pm S.E., n=3.

Groundwater characteristics

The groundwater salinity was significant along this transect ($F = 11.03$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest salinity reading occurred in Zone 3 (76.4 ppt). The lowest salinity reading was at 274 m (Zone 4 = 10.5 ppt, $p < 0.05$, S.E. = 3.0). The highest salinity reading was at 90 m (Zone 2 = 68.0 ppt, S.E. = 4.8) and the lowest reading was at 274 m (Zone 4 = 10.5 ppt, S.E. = 3.0) (Fig 26a). The salinity at Zone 4 was significantly less than the salinity at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$) and at 150 m (Zone 3 = 61.5 ppt, S.E. = 26.0, $p < 0.05$).

The groundwater electrical conductivity had a similar trend as the groundwater salinity and was significant along this transect ($F = 12.48$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The highest electrical conductivity reading was at 90 m (Zone 2 = 94.7 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 5.7) and the lowest reading was at 274 m (Zone 4 = 17.7 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 4.7) (Fig 26b). The electrical conductivity at Zone 4 was significantly less than the conductivity at Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$) and at 150 m (Zone 3 = 85.7 mS cm⁻¹, S.E. = 32.5, $p < 0.05$).

The depth to the groundwater table was significant along this transect ($H = 10.57$, d.f. = 3, $p < 0.05$). The depth increased along the transect from 15 m (Zone 1 = 0.0 cm, S.E. = 0.0) to 274 m (Zone 4 = 148.3 cm, S.E. = 7.6) (Fig 26c). The depth to groundwater at Zone 1 was significantly less than at 90 m (Zone 2 = 13.3 cm, S.E. = 5.8, $p < 0.05$), 150 m (Zone 3 = 88.3 cm, S.E. = 25.7, $p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The depth to groundwater at Zone 2 was significantly less than at Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 4 ($p < 0.05$). The depth to groundwater at Zone 4 was significantly greater than at Zone 1 ($p < 0.05$), Zone 2 ($p < 0.05$) and Zone 3 ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 26. Groundwater characteristics along Transect 6. Vertical bars = \pm S.E, n=3.

Habitat distribution

The vegetation was analysed with Detrended Correspondence Analysis (DCA) (Fig 27). Elevation significantly influenced the distribution of plant communities along this transect. *Triglochin buchenau*, *Salicornia meyeriana* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* occurred where there was a shallow depth to the groundwater table (DCA1 = -0.211, DCA2 = 0.977, $r^2 = 0.576$, $p < 0.05$) and where the elevation was low, while *Atriplex cinerea* and *Lycium cinereum* occurred at high elevations (DCA1 = -0.846, DCA2 = 0.533, $r^2 = 0.576$, $p < 0.05$) and where the depth to the groundwater table was greater. *Triglochin buchenau* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* was also influenced by high sediment pH (DCA1 = 0.239, DCA2 = -0.971, $r^2 = 0.262$, $p < 0.05$) and high sediment electrical conductivity (DCA1 = -0.994, DCA2 = -0.113, $r^2 = 0.585$, $p < 0.05$). *Salicornia meyeriana* was influenced by low sediment electrical conductivity, increased redox (DCA1 = 0.357, DCA2 = 0.934, $r^2 = 0.262$, $p < 0.05$) and low sediment moisture content (DCA1 = -0.948, DCA2 = -0.320, $r^2 = 0.554$, $p < 0.05$). *Salicornia meyeriana* was influenced by high sediment organic content (DCA1 = -0.384, DCA2 = -0.924, $r^2 = 0.272$, $p < 0.05$). The elevation seemed to be the most determining factor in terms of species distribution and thus no distinct communities could be determined.

Figure 27: DCA plot of species and environmental factors along transect 6. Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.88, 2=0.538, 3=0.275, 4=0.262. Total inertia = 4.051.

4.8 Correlation of environmental variables

Spearman correlation analysis revealed the relationships among the environmental factors that affect the distribution of salt marsh species (Fig 28). The various correlations are indicated below.

Sediment moisture content was significantly positively correlated to sediment organic matter ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$) and to sediment electrical conductivity ($r = 0.74$, $p < 0.05$, $n=78$). The sediment moisture content was negatively correlated to sediment pH ($r=-0.40$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$), sediment redox potential ($r = -0.28$, $p < 0.05$ $n = 78$) and depth to the groundwater table ($r = -0.30$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 75$).

The sediment organic content was positively correlated to sediment moisture ($r = 0.76$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$) and to sediment electrical conductivity ($r = 0.59$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$) and was negatively correlated to sediment pH ($r = -0.26$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$).

Sediment electrical conductivity was positively correlated to sediment moisture ($r = 0.74$, $p < 0.05$, $n=78$) and to sediment organic content ($r = 0.56$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$,) and was negatively correlated to sediment pH ($r = -0.33$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 78$).

Groundwater electrical conductivity / salinity was negatively correlated to depth to the ground water table ($r = -0.51$, $p < 0.05$, $n = 75$).

Figure 28. Correlations between the various environmental factors across each of the transects.

4.9 Habitat distribution of Langebaan salt marshes

The vegetation was analysed with Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA). The Constrained Correspondence Analysis (CCA) showed that the vegetation distribution along each of the transects were affected by various environmental factors (Fig 29).

The species distribution along each transect seemed to be influenced by groundwater depth and electrical conductivity. Species such as *Salicornia meyeriana*, *Spartina maritima* and *Sarcocornia pillansii* occurred where there was high sand content (CA1 = -0.569, CA2 = 0.822, $r^2 = 0.09$, $p < 0.05$), little depth to the groundwater table and where there was a high groundwater electrical conductivity / salinity, while other species such as *Euphorbia mauretanicus* and *Lycium tetrandrum* occurred where there was a high silt content (CA1 = 0.678, CA2 = -0.735, $r^2 = 0.042$, $p < 0.05$) a greater depth to groundwater (CA1 = 0.674, CA2 = -0.738, $r^2 = 0.09$, $p < 0.05$) and the groundwater was less saline (CA1 = -0.80, CA2 = 0.60, $r^2 = 0.10$, $p < 0.05$). Sediment moisture also played an influencing role on the salt marsh distribution. The salt marsh species situated nearest to water bodies, i.e. intertidal species such as *Spartina maritima* and *Sarcocornia tegetaria* were influenced by high sediment moisture content (CA1 = -0.211, CA2 = 0.977, $r^2 = 0.18$, $p < 0.05$). *Juncus kraussii* and *Lycium cinereum* were influenced by a high sediment organic content (CA1 = 0.307, CA2 = 0.952, $r^2 = 0.14$, $p < 0.05$) and high sediment electrical conductivity (CA1 = 0.016, CA2 = 0.999, $r^2 = 0.05$, $p < 0.05$). *Juncus acutus*, *Lycium tetrandrum* and other species associated with occurring at a high depth to groundwater was influenced by increases in pH (CA1 = 0.988, CA2 = -0.157, $r^2 = 0.08$, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 29. CCA plot of species and environmental factors along each transect (1-6). Eigenvalues axis 1 = 0.809, 2=0.792, 3=.750, 4=0.717. Total inertia = 10.87.

4.10 Species Communities within Langebaan

The following table indicates the various salt marsh species occurring in the intertidal, intertidal-supratidal and supratidal zones, as described by Boucher and Jarman (1977), O'Callaghan (1994) and this current study. Each zone described by the different authors appears to be different.

Boucher and Jarman identified (1977) a *Juncus* – *Scirpus* community and a *Bassia* – *Salicornia* community, which consists of two forms: The *Limonium* – *Disphyma* form and *Spartina* – *Triglochin* form. Intertidal and supratidal species were not clearly indicated by Jarman and Boucher (1977).

O'Callaghan (1994) described communities based on the position of salt marsh species according to elevation. The lower salt marsh communities were situated below the mean sea level up to the mean high water neap, the upper salt marsh communities were situated above the spring high mark and the middle salt marsh communities were situated between the low and high salt marsh communities.

This study found two monospecific stands of *Juncus kraussii* and *Juncus acutus*. The other community types were the intertidal, intertidal-supratidal and supratidal zones. The intertidal and supratidal communities with associated species are indicated in Table 4 below.

Table 4: Salt marsh community types as classified by various authours.

	O'Callaghan, 1994	Boucher and Jarman, 1977	2014
Intertidal	<i>Zostera capensis</i>	<i>Bassia diffusa</i>	<i>Zostera capensis</i>
	<i>Schoenoplectus triqueter</i>	<i>Salicornia meyerana</i>	<i>Schoenoplectus triqueter</i>
	<i>Spartina maritima</i>	<i>Disphyma crassifolia</i>	<i>Spartina maritima</i>
		<i>Limonium equisetum</i>	<i>Bassia diffusa</i>
		<i>Triglochin bolbosa</i>	<i>Triglochin buchenau</i>
		<i>Spartina maritima</i>	<i>Sarcocornia tegetaria</i>
		<i>Lycium tetrandrum</i>	<i>Limonium linifolium</i>
		<i>Spergularia media</i>	
Intertidal-Supratidal	<i>Triglochin bulbosa</i>	<i>Disphyma crassifolia</i>	<i>Bassia diffusa</i>
	<i>Sarcocornia perennis</i>	<i>Limonium equisetum</i>	<i>Triglochin buchenau</i>
	<i>Limonium depauperatum</i>	<i>Bassia diffusa</i>	<i>Sarcocornia tegetaria</i>
	<i>Bassia diffusa</i>	<i>Triglochin bolbosa</i>	<i>Limonium linifolium</i>
		<i>Spartina maritima</i>	<i>Atriplex cinerea</i>
			<i>Limonium linifolia</i>
			<i>Sarcocornia uniflora</i>
			<i>Sarcocornia tegetaria</i>
			<i>Sporobolus virginicus</i>
			<i>Salicornia meyeriana</i>
Supratidal	<i>Atriplex cinerea</i>		<i>Salicornia meyeriana</i>
	<i>Cotula eckloniana</i>		<i>Sarcocornia pillansii</i>
	<i>Crassula decumbens</i>		<i>Limonium linifolia</i>
	<i>Dimorphotheca pulvialis</i>		<i>Spergularia media</i>
	<i>Disphyma crassifolium</i>		<i>Sporobolus virginicus</i>
	<i>Drosanthemum delicatulum</i>		<i>Atriplex semibaccata</i>
	<i>Juncus kraussii</i>		<i>Sporobolus fimbristilus</i>
	<i>Limonium depauperatum</i>		<i>Limonium depauperatum</i>
	<i>Lolium perenne</i>		<i>Triglochin elongata</i>
	<i>Othonna perfoliata</i>		
	<i>Oxalis pes-caprae</i>		
	<i>Plantago crassifolia</i>		
	<i>Puccinellia angusta</i>		
	<i>Romulea tabularis</i>		
	<i>Salicornia meyeriana</i>		
	<i>Sarcocornia littorea</i>		
	<i>Sarcocornia pillansii</i>		
	<i>Senecio littoreus</i>		
	<i>Sporobolus virginicus</i>		
	<i>Suaeda inflata</i>		
	<i>Tetragonia decumbens</i>		
	<i>Tetragonia fruticosa</i>		
	<i>Trachyandra divaricata</i>		
<i>Triglochin bulbosa</i>			
<i>Triglochin stiata</i>			

5. Discussion

5.1 Environmental factors and species distribution

The dominant vegetation type within the salt marsh was the intertidal salt marsh and the supratidal salt marsh, each making up 23% of the total salt marsh vegetation type. Langebaan is a coastal embayment type estuary lacking a riverine input and contains a large intertidal area. Large intertidal salt marsh areas are considered to be rare as only 18% of South African estuaries are permanently open estuaries containing intertidal zones (Bornman *et al.*, 2008). The hypothesis that the vegetation at Langebaan responds similarly to traditional estuarine salt marshes was accepted as the Langebaan salt marshes has similar features to traditional estuaries in terms of having intertidal, supratidal and terrestrial zones. These zones were caused due to a number of influencing environmental factors.

This study indicated that groundwater electrical conductivity and depth to the groundwater table had a significant influence on the different salt marsh vegetation at Langebaan. However it was not the only environmental variable that contributed to the distribution of salt marsh species. Sediment moisture content, organic content, pH, redox and electrical conductivity and sediment composition (sand and silt) also influenced the vegetation distribution along Langebaan salt marshes (Fig 26). The groundwater depth within the supratidal and terrestrial zones was generally 70 cm deep and was significantly deeper than within the intertidal zones. The groundwater salinity was significantly higher in the intertidal zones than the supratidal and terrestrial zones and was generally greater than 25 ppt. Thus the hypothesis that groundwater influences salt marsh species distribution was accepted. The extent at which groundwater influences the salt marsh vegetation is unknown and future research is needed to determine the true functions and roles that groundwater has on the salt marsh communities.

Reaper (1995) and Fariña *et al.* (2009) found that no single environmental factor could influence species distribution within salt marshes. Tabot and Adams (2013) found that salt marshes are susceptible to fluctuations in environmental factors due to their unique placements along the South African coasts. Elevation had an effect on various environmental factors such as sediment nutrients and electrical conductivity previously in Langebaan (Reaper, 1995). Flooding frequency decreases and low sediment salinities occur at high elevations. This study found that the three transects at Geelbek (Transect

1, 2 and 6) were significantly influenced by elevation. These transects at Geelbek were however not the only salt marsh that had displayed vegetation zonations during this study. Angiolini et al. (2013) found that distance from the coastline, rather than elevation drove the vegetation composition and distribution in salt marshes. Distance from water bodies does influence the vegetation distribution. This was observed in this study as *Spartina maritima* occurred in moist areas within the intertidal and intertidal – supratidal zones, while *Sarcocornia pillansii* occurred within areas that are low in sediment moisture. Throughout the various transects, each environmental variable displayed different trends, indicating that each salt marsh is unique in its characteristics. Transect 1 and 2 at Geelbek had a distinct intertidal and supratidal zone, while the transect at Preekstoel had an additional intertidal-supratidal zone. Transect 6 did not have distinct zones, but a distinct elevation gradient where species were distributed. Differences in environmental relationships within the different salt marshes are a possible reason for mosaic vegetation patterns that were observed, particularly at Transect 1 and 5.

According to Pennings & Callaway (1992), sediment moisture content is a key influencing factor of salt marsh distributions as it can alter sediment redox potentials and pH, which in effect can influence nutrient and oxygen availability. Kim and Yu (2009) found that moisture and organic matter increased along a gradient from the water edge of salt marshes to the terrestrial zones, while the pH and salinity decreased. Özcan et al. (2010) and Angiolini et al. (2013) found salinity to be the key limiting factor within salt marsh communities. The results from this study indicate that there is no one key limiting factor influencing a salt marsh. This study found that there were a number of correlating environmental factors (see Fig 28) and that environmental factors influenced the vegetation distribution differently along each transect. With this being said, a correlation existed between sediment moisture, redox potential and pH suggests that sediment moisture content may well be an important factor influencing salt marsh vegetation. Sediment moisture content influenced the vegetation at various salt marshes within Langebaan. Reaper (1995) found similar results to this study. The sediment moisture content varied throughout the different salt marshes and within intertidal / supratidal areas. In some cases, such as at Transect 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6, the sediment at the water edge had a less moisture content than within areas in the salt marsh. Fine sediments in these zones may play a role in water retention in these areas. This can be supported by means of the water edge containing a high silt content (containing particle sizes of 0.05 – 0.002 mm), while the intertidal / supratidal regions were higher in clay content (containing particle sizes of less than 0.002 mm). Salinity has been known to follow a

similar trend to that of moisture within salt marshes. Salinity can increase from *Spartina maritima* beds into intertidal and/or intertidal-supratidal zones. This has occurred throughout the transects of this study. Langebaan has a low freshwater input and occurs in a semi-arid area, which can influence the accumulation of salinity within these zones due to high evaporation rates (Murphy et al., 2003).

The sediment pH recorded during this study at each transect was higher than the pH recorded by Boucher and Jarman (1977). There are a number of reasons that could have led to an increase in sediment pH. The most likely reason for the increase in pH may be that pH fluctuates due to seasonal changes and upwelling events (Hofmann et al., 2011).

Inundation and salinity stress have also known to play roles in determining vegetation distributions within salt marshes (He et al., 2009; Cui et al., 2011). *Suaeda* species have a wide tolerance range to salinity and inundation stress (He et al., 2009). *Suaeda inflata* occurred at Langebaan at Transect 1, 2 and 4. Along transect 1 *S. inflata* occurred in the intertidal – supratidal zone, the supratidal zone along Transect 2 and in the intertidal zone along Transect 3. Although environmental factors can influence species distributions, species specific adaptations also determine species distributions (Cui et al., 2011).

According to Boucher & Jarman (1977) the *Bassia* - *Salicornia* community was the main community within Langebaan salt marshes, distributed in a mosaic pattern comprising of *Limonium* – *Disphyma* and *Spartina* – *Triglochin* sub-communities. The mosaic pattern of salt marsh vegetation was apparent during this study. This lack of vegetation zonation was also observed by Reaper (1995) who indicated that mosaic patterns are a result of low tidal amplifications and this pattern has been observed by other authors such as (Adam, 1981; Rozema et al., 1985). Boucher & Jarman (1977) and Reaper (1995) also indicated that salt marshes at Langebaan can be characterised by *Sarcocornia pillansii*. This study found that *S. pillansii* was found within every salt marsh at Langebaan, but was not densely populated throughout all the intertidal / supratidal salt marshes. *Sarcocornia pillansii* tends to dominate salt marsh areas that are low in sediment moisture content (less than 5%) and high in sediment electrical conductivity (greater than 40 mS cm⁻¹), (Bezuidenhout 2011) and is related to great depth to the groundwater table and high salinity of groundwater (Bornman, 2002; Bornman et al., 2004).

Juncus kraussii and *J. acutus* patches were found in areas of depressions at Geelbek and the sediment electrical conductivity within these two patches reached between 36 – 64 mS cm⁻¹ and 32 – 46 mS cm⁻¹ respectively. The groundwater salinity within the *J. kraussii* patch was high (37 ppt), while the groundwater salinity within *J. acutus* was low (12 ppt). This suggests that *J. kraussii* may be more tolerant to salinities than *J. acutus* or that *J. kraussii* occasionally is exposed to freshwater.

5.2 Management of Langebaan salt marshes

Defining set targets

Management practices that did not have proper defining targets have resulted in extensive losses of macrophytes around the world (Kennish, 2001; Jefferies and Rockwell, 2002; Pett-Ridge and Firestone, 2005; Martone and Wasson, 2008). The management aim of any salt marsh is to maintain the dynamic system and other associated systems surrounding it. Management begins with setting guidelines that relate to the salt marsh. In order to set guidelines, strategic ecological conservation studies and decisions need to be made. Salt marshes have the ability to change over time as a result of these systems being dynamic (de Groot *et al.*, 2011). Since these systems may be prone to changes over time, it is crucial that continual environmental monitoring is set to understand changes over time and to successfully alter management guidelines if necessary. Management success is not simply determined by species and communities present in a given area, as functioning and stability are also important factors to consider (Boorman, 2003). Key processes to setting environmental guideline is by gathering recent information relating to salt marsh species, communities and interactions between biotic and abiotic factors. Thus there is a great need for management plans to be updated and assessed as new scientific knowledge becomes accessible. Changes of species density and distributions also need to be taken into consideration as to identify crucial areas of conservation and to enhance the knowledge of species functions within a system.

As part of any environmental management and conservation strategy, a continuously updated database of species occurring within different vegetation types at Langebaan needs to be drawn up and can be used as a monitoring technique. Mace (2004) explained that species databases are always going to be subject to change as species definitions change due to taxonomic differences. However, with climate changes and various

influences it may have on salt marshes species are likely to change as well. Important species to consider for conservation purposes are those endemic to South Africa, threatened, endangered and rare. Not all macrophytes are of a significant conservation value as many are globally distributed. However there are some endemic *Sarcocornia* and *Triglochin* species that are endemic and threatened to South Africa (Köcke et al., 2010; Steffen et al., 2010). By providing and including estuarine experts and managers with database information, species can accurately be identified. This is important as management plans can be only protect species that are identified (Veldkornet, 2011).

Changes over time

Langebaan salt marshes have changed over time. Gericke (2008) studied changes in salt marshes within the Langebaan area and the results to his study indicated that the salt marsh areas have decreased and a loss of small salt marshes was observed between the years of 1960 – 2000. The possible cause of this was sea level rise (see Gericke 2008). Sea level rise is relative to the surface of salt marshes and all environmental factors will be affected. Schmidt (2013) explained that as soils are likely to become more waterlogged up the elevation gradient, the aeration within sediments will be reduced and the redox potential will be affected. If salt marshes are able to move landwards relatively equals the rate at which the sea level rises, the sediment type will also influence the salt marsh. Sand particles are generally more associated with terrestrial zones, which contain larger pore sizes to the other sediment types, which may not store nutrients as well as other sediment types.

The West Coast National Park Management Plan described the salt marsh vegetation to that of Jarman and Boucher (1977). This study found a difference in species communities to that described by Boucher and Jarman (1977). According to Boucher and Jarman (1977) and O’Callaghan (1994), the salt marshes were characterised by the most dominant species being *Sarcocornia pillansii*. This study found that *Sarcocornia tegeteria* was the most dominant species within the salt marshes and *S. pillansii* came second to that. *S. pillansii* was a dominant species within the intertidal – supratidal zone. Change in *S. pillansii* could be an indicator of climate change within the Langebaan system. As the sea level rises and rainfall increases over time, it can be predicted that *S. pillansii* populations will decrease in density as a response to an increase in moisture content throughout the salt marsh.

Before the West Coast National Park, the Langebaan vegetation was threatened by invasive species, such as *Acacia cyclops* and *Acacia saligna*. The salt marsh *Bassia* - *Salicornia* community described by Boucher and Jarman (1977) was greatly disturbed by vehicles and overgrazing of domesticated animals (horses, goats, sheep and ostriches). Sheep were removed from Langebaan in 1993 and by 1994, *Sarcocornia pillansii* and *Suaeda inflata* had extended its growth at Transect 2 and 6 (southwest of Geelbek and west of Geelbek) (O'Callaghan, 1994). Signs of grazing can still be observed at the salt marsh area west of Geelbek. Grazing has impacted salt marsh worldwide. Grazing has the potential to eliminate rare species (Laegdsgaard, 2006), increase bare soil and thus increase salinity in the supratidal zones of salt marshes (Yu and Chmura, 2010).

Reaper 1995 considered *Zostera capensis* (eelgrass) to be part of the salt marsh community as he found it to be interspread in *Spartina maritima* dominated areas. Eelgrass has an important ecological role to play in terms of nutrient cycling (Christie, 1981). Eelgrass is however sensitive to environmental changes and has been declining in salt marsh systems throughout the world (Waycott *et al.*, 2009). Hughes *et al.* (2002) indicated that eelgrass beds are important features of Langebaan as they act as nurseries for fish and as foraging areas for birds. The Oosterval area at Langebaan has lost an extended amount of its eelgrass beds and in its place sand flats have formed. The borrowing sand prawn (*Callinassa kraussi*) has colonised these sand flats, preventing eelgrass from re-colonising. The loss of eelgrass and long term effects associated are not well understood. Monitoring these changes is crucial for the understanding of changing community structures. Orth *et al.* (2006) suggested that the loss of eelgrass beds and its associated species could have a cascading effect on high trophic organisms. The WCNP: Management Plan did cover the loss of eelgrass as part of the key issues, but no evaluation or monitoring plan has been prepared.

Environmental plans are a crucial component of conservation and needs to be updated on a regular basis. Literature used to define components of a salt marsh should be updated regularly. Using literature that was published more than 10 years ago may not be relevant as changes have been occurring rapidly. Salt marshes are important for carbon sequestrating, nutrient import and export, flood and erosion control, refuge and habitat area. Salt marshes also have aesthetic value and are important for tourism and it is essential that these systems are preserved and conserved as the study of such systems is also of education and research value.

6. Conclusion

This study indicated that Langebaan Lagoon salt marshes are similar in structure and distribution to other South African salt marshes. The conservation of salt marshes is important as they hold a great a great deal of foraging fauna species and halophyte species are only adapted to grow in salt marshes. A loss of these systems would mean a loss of vegetation would occur and loss of associated fauna species. Thus the conservation of salt marshes should be nationally prioritised, especially with the unpredictable changes associated with climate change.

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